

Need of UAVs and Physical Layer Security in Next-generation Non-terrestrial Wireless Networks: Potential Challenges and Open Issues

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This work is supported by Mobility and Training for Beyond 5G Ecosystems (MOTOR5G), funded under European Union's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions Innovative Training Network having grant agreement no. 861219.

ABSTRACT Recent revolutionary advancements in the services as observed with the use cases of Industry 5.0, consumer electronics 2.0/smart devices 2.0, digital healthcare ecosystem, Internet-of-Things (IoT), advanced digital finance/currency, and Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) expansion, to name a few, have resulted in a spectacular growth in the number of wireless-connected devices. Subsequently, this has drastically increased the demands for network capacity, channel capacity, reliability, privacy, and security provisions. Despite that, the 5th Generation (5G) of wireless communication networks has introduced various innovative services such as Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communication (URLLCs), Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTCs), and Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB). These services only support isolated operations and the requisite reliable service delivery remains a challenge. The Beyond 5G (B5G)/6th Generation (6G) wireless networks aim at simultaneously providing multiple integrated services through intelligent network operations with ultra-high speed and reliability supporting integrated NTN and terrestrial networks. However, the prospect of such an extensively connected decentralized 3D wireless network also foresees security concerns, underscoring the necessity for seamless and infrastructure-free (decentralized) security solutions. The conventional security mechanisms are considered inadequate to ensure the security provisions of such extensive, decentralized, and heterogeneous networks. Physical Layer Security (PLS) is a promising technique to extend seamless and infrastructure-less security solutions, ensuring the availability, confidentiality, and integrity of legitimate transmissions. This paper provides a comprehensive overview with tutorials and presents the state-of-the-art of PLS, focusing mainly on NTN wireless communications. Furthermore, current research challenges, open issues, and future research directions are also thoroughly discussed in an amalgamation of various emerging 6G technologies. Finally, we provide an overview of implementation challenges in NTN and potential solutions to support the standardization progression of NTN in upcoming releases of 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP).

INDEX TERMS 5G, 6G, Non-Terrestrial Networks, Physical Layer, Privacy, Security, Secret Key Generation, UAVs-enabled Communication

I. Introduction

THE drastic expansion in the Internet-of-Things (IoTs) devices and the emerging digitization concepts such as Industry 5.0 (I5.0) are leading to transformations in the business and consumer worlds, igniting a new industrial revolution [1]. Records indicate that as of 2020, over 9 billion linked devices [2] are in existence. In 1999, Kevin Ashton of MIT introduced the term IoT to describe a network that links not just people but also nearby things or items [3]. In 2009, the number of IoT devices outnumbered the number of humans in terms of connectivity [4], and presently, IoT devices such as smartphones, sensors, autonomous vehicles, Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and wearable devices are interconnected and used to collect and analyze data to perform specific actions. According to the forecast report published by the Transforma Insights, the number of IoT devices will cross 30 billion by 2030, including 39 million specialized connected robots supporting humans in different industries like the automotive industry, restaurants, hospitals, and many more [5]. The expected growth is from 384 to 566.4 billion dollars from 2021 to 2027, with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 6.7% [6] shows that it is necessary to provide massive connectivity and to fulfill the data rates and latency requirements.

Considering the future needs, the 5th Generation (5G) networks are standardized with a focus on enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) capable of providing 100 Mbps to users, 20 Gbps throughput with 1 ms latency [7]. However, one user cannot access all three services simultaneously, which limits the capability of 5G. Moreover, researchers have anticipated that 5G capabilities may not be sufficient to fulfill the drastically increasing capacity demands beyond a decade or so (i.e., beyond 2030) [8]. With the deployment of 5G wireless communication networks, the total number of connected people to the internet at the beginning of 2023 has been recorded as 5.16 billion, which constitutes around 64% of the population [9]. In 6th Generation networks (6G), the global coverage is aimed to be enhanced to provide Artificial Intelligence (AI) and big data services, ensuring security with high reuse spectrum factors. The application and security services can be achieved with communications schemes like Terahertz (THz) [10], sub-bands of 6 GHz [11], and millimeter Wave (mmwave) [12]. Still, geographic coverage is not possible with the conventional terrestrial 5G networks. Hence, terrestrial and Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) integration has been proposed as a feature of 6G wireless systems adopting a three-layer service approach. The first layer consists of satellites, the second layer contains UAVs, and the last layer consists of terrestrial Base Station (BS) [13]. UAVs play a significant role in NTNs due

to maneuverability, easy and rapid deployment, and cost-effectiveness.

The importance of UAVs is drastically escalating. Based on the application, there have been made different forecasts for the growth of the UAV market value. According to forecast reports published in September 2022 by Market-sandMarkets and TechSciResearch, the predicted growth is 38.3 billion dollars with a CAGR of 7.9% (2019-2027) [14], and 96 billion dollars with a CAGR of 17.99% (2017-2027) [15], respectively. The UAVs were primarily considered for reconnaissance, surveillance, and other military applications and then adopted for civilian applications in agriculture, package delivery, etc. [16]. The UAV was first used in World War II, invented by R. Denny, known as Radioplane OQ – 2, and considered a breakthrough in the military manufacturing industry [17], [18]. With the advancement of technologies, every field is emerging and adopting digitization and automation, such as I5.0, hyper-connected societies, and digital twins, which is impossible without wireless connectivity. The expansion of these technologies results in fast data rates, massive connectivity, low latency, and reliability, which can not be achieved with the existing 5G standards. Zong *et al.* proposed in [19] that Ubiquitous Mobile Ultra-Broadband (UMUB), Ultra-High Data Density (UHDD), and Ultra-High Speed Low Latency communications (UHSLLC) are the 6G technologies, which can address the needs for fast data rates, massive connectivity, and low latency communications respectively.

In NTN-6G mobile networks, UAVs are considered to provide connectivity to remote areas, disaster areas, and bottleneck situations, depending on the needs. UAVs can be classified into High Altitude Platform (HAP) and Low Altitude Platform (LAP) [20]. HAP is used to provide connectivity in remote areas and was first tested by Google, known as the LOON project, used to provide connectivity from 32 km altitude to oil companies and conveyors in the south region of the United States [21], [22]. HAPs are usually fly-in stratosphere zones starting from 20 km to 50 km [23] and designed for long-endurance flights, i.e., ranges from a few days to many months. The LAPs deployed at low altitudes, depending on the mission, area, and atmospheric conditions, and were designed for applications that required short flight time. The deployment of LAP is easier as compared to the deployment of HAP, although the trajectory design is a bit difficult due to the short-range [24]. Generally, LAPs are used in emergency scenarios such as flood situations, landslides, and vehicle tracking. In contrast, HAPs are used to enable communications in remote areas, as they are considered quasi-static in reference to Earth.

These UAVs can be used in NTNs as an Aerial Base Station (ABS) [25] or Aerial Relay (AR) [26]. *For instance, providing wireless connectivity to the disaster area through rotational ABS to expand coverage with minimal cost has been proposed in [27] while optimizing the response through efficient trajectory planning with a genetic algorithm has*

TABLE 1. List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/ Acronym	Definition	Abbreviation/ Acronym	Definition
2D	Two Dimensional	LAP	Low Altitude Platform
3D	Three Dimensional	LCR	Level Crossing Rate
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project	LDPC	Low Density Parity Check
5G	5 th Generation Wireless Communication Networks	LEO	Low Earth Orbital
6G	6 th Generation Wireless Communication Networks	LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
A2A	Air-to-Air	LOS	Line of Sight
A2G	Air-to-Ground	LSTM	Long-Short Term Memory
ABS	Aerial Base Station	LTE	Long Term Evolution
ACD	Average Contiguous Duration	Mbps	Megabits Per Second
AFD	Average Fade Duration	MEC	Multiple Access Edge Computing
AI	Artificial Intelligence	MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
AN	Artificial Noise	ML	Machine Learning
AoA	Angle of Arrival	mMIMO	Massive MIMO
AR	Aerial Relay	mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communications
AUE	Aerial User Equipment	mmWave	Millimeter Wave
AWGN	Additive White Gaussian Noise	MRT	Maximum Rate Transmission
BER	Bit Error Rate	MSDBC	Memoryless-State Dependent Broadcast Channels
BLER	Block Error Rate	NGEO	Non-Geostationary Earth Orbital
BS	Base Station	NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
C2	Command and Control	NLOS	Non-Line of Sight
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate	NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
CDR	Channel Dimensionality Reduction	NR	New Radio
CEF	Continuous Encryption Function	NTN	Non-Terrestrial Networks
CNN	Convolution Neural Network	OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access
CSI	Channel State Information	OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
D2D	Device to Device	OSI	Open System Interconnection
DES	Data Encryption Standard	PLS	Physical Layer Security
DP	Delay Profile	PM	Pathloss Model
EE	Energy Efficiency	PPM	Pulse Position Modulation
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband	PS	Power Station
FCS	Flight Control System	PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
FDD	Frequency-Division Duplexing	QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
Gbps	Gigabits Per Second	QoE	Quality of Experience
GBS	Ground Base Station	QoS	Quality of Service
GCS	Ground Control Stations	RIS	Re-Configurable Intelligent Surfaces
GEO	Geostationary Earth Orbital	RL	Reinforcement Learning
GHz	Gigahertz	RML	Receiver Message Linkability
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System	RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
GPS	Global Positioning System	RSMA	Rate Splitting Multiple Access
GUE	Ground User Equipment	RSS	Received Signal Strength
HAP	High Altitude Platform	RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
HD	High Definition	SAGSIN	Space-Air-Ground-Sea Integrated Networks
I5.0	Industry 5.0	SAIN	Satellite and Aerial Integrated Networks
ICI	Inter-Carrier Interference	SCP	Successive Convex Approximation
IoT	Internet-of-Things	SDMA	Space Division Multiplexing
IRS	Intelligent Reflecting Surfaces	SKG	Secret Key Generation
ITUSN	Integrated Terrestrial-UAV-Satellite Networks	SKG	Secret Key Generation
KAP	Key Agreement Probability	SL	Supervisor Learning
KGR	Key Generation Rate	SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
KMP	Key Mismatch Probability	SOP	Secrecy Outage Probability

TABLE 2. Continue: List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/ Acronym	Definition	Abbreviation/ Acronym	Definition
SR	Secrecy Rate	URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
SSL	Semi-Supervised Learning	US	Uncorrelated Scattering
ST	Secrecy Throughput	USL	Unsupervised Learning
SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power	UT	User Terminal
SWIPT	Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transfer	UTM	UAV Traffic Management
TDD	Time-Division Duplexing	VLC	Visible Light Communications
TLS	Terrestrial Laser Sensing	VR	Virtual Reality
UAV	Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle	WCSR	Worst Case Secrecy Rate
UHDD	Ultra-High Data Density	WIT	Wireless Information Transfer
UHSLLC	Ultra-High Speed Low Latency Communications	WPT	Wireless Power Transfer
UMUB	Ubiquitous Mobile Ultra-Broadband	WSS	Wide Sense Stationary

been proposed in [28]. Similarly, UAV as AR, has been discussed with a tutorial view in [29], and a secure approach for the air-to-ground users based on proceed-hover-return has been proposed in [30]. The channel models are more complex in NTN as compared to terrestrial networks due to the three-dimensional (3D), unique, scarce propagation, and frequently changing deployments [31]. On the contrary, terrestrial BS is considered a two-dimensional (2D), well-established propagation, permanent, and fixed deployment. These properties of the multi-layer communication model and wide coverage in NTNs make it easier for attackers to locate and intercept signals, making consumers' information vulnerable to jamming and spoofing [32]. An approach for modelling the interaction between the terrestrial BS and ABS for disaster recovery situations has been proposed in [33]. In the NTN case, infrastructure-based security is uncertain due to weight and power limitations. Therefore, it has been proposed that the physical layer in the wireless networks is the first to be exploited and can be used to ensure infrastructure-less secure communication. The vision of NTN in cellular communications and IoT applications has been given in [34], which focuses on channel code design and technologies that can be used in 6G-NTN networks. Different types of threats, such as physical, operational, network information, and countermeasures are discussed [35]. The importance of UAVs in cellular communications in different propagation environments and standardization in 5G and 6G have been considered for review in [11], [36]. The role of satellites in NTN and the architecture of Geostationary Earth Orbital (GEO) satellites and Non-GEO (NGEO) satellites in terms of network slicing and resource management have been discussed in [37]. The technologies that could be used in 6G-NTN on each Open System Interconnection (OSI) layer have been reviewed in [38], and challenges and open issues in physical and network layers were discussed. The security aspects in 6G communication networks are also considered with different 6G technologies [39], and the attacks and their mitigation techniques in wireless communications have been

analyzed in [40]. However, space and ocean communications are not included in the context of [39], [40].

Considering the importance of UAVs in wireless communications, lots of wireless communications researchers are working in this domain. Considering and addressing security threats is significantly important to ensure safe and reliable communication. This paper provides an extensive review of PLS in NTN wireless communications. This review is to fill the gaps in the needed detailed analysis of potential security schemes and the role of the NTN in 6G wireless networks. The contributions and organization of this review paper are the following:

- Considering the needs of industries, we analyze the channel models for two use cases, and the potential solution of UAVs in NTN wireless communications is discussed in Section II.
- We introduce the layered stack approach in NTN wireless communications, i.e., the first layer consists of a constellation of satellites, the second layer contains the HAPs, the third layer LAPs, the fourth layer ground, and the fifth and last layer contains ocean and under-water communications.
- This paper also presents a technical review of PLS techniques from fundamental concepts to future trends in Section III. Furthermore, the tutorial aspects of this section offer comprehensive insights into the foundation of information-theoretic secrecy analysis. This section delves into the fundamental principles and theoretical foundation of information security, providing a detailed exploration of the key attributes that define secure communication systems. It also emphasizes crucial key performance indicators that are essential for evaluating and enhancing the effectiveness of secrecy measures. By thoroughly explaining these concepts, the section aims to equip readers with a deep understanding of the core elements and metrics involved in information-theoretic secrecy, thereby facilitating a more informed and robust approach to security analysis.

- We discuss the current trends, future direction, and open issues in technologies pivotal to 6G NTN wireless communications. In Section IV, a comprehensive analysis is provided, highlighting the recent trends shaping the NTN landscape. We identify potential areas for future research and development and discuss the challenges that need to be addressed.
- This paper reviews physical layer attacks and countermeasures and discusses the viability of the recommended solutions. The emphasis on PLS is due to the prevalence of attacks such as jamming and eavesdropping at the physical layer, contrasting with conventional upper-layer security designs. PLS offers advantages such as cost-effectiveness, infrastructure independence, and Energy Efficiency (EE) with a minimal latency impact. Consequently, the exclusive reliance on PLS strategies is pre-eminent for most industrial use cases.
- From an industrial perspective, the security of UAVs and information is desired, especially in critical missions. This paper presents the performance evaluation and challenges in UAVs in different use cases, and an overview of information security is discussed in Section V and Section VI.
- This paper discusses various technical and practical issues that may arise during the implementation process and suggests potential solutions and strategies to address them in Section VII. Through this comprehensive analysis, the paper aims to equip researchers with the necessary insights to effectively tackle these challenges and advance the development of 6G-NTN wireless communications.

FIGURE 1. Structure of the paper

The structure of the paper is given in Fig. 1, and the acronyms and abbreviations used throughout the paper are listed in Table 1 and Table 2. For the survey conducted in this paper, we utilized several prominent academic databases: Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus. These databases were chosen for their comprehensive coverage of scholarly literature across various disciplines, ensuring a thorough exploration of existing research related to our topic. By exploiting these databases, we ensured that our survey encompassed diverse perspectives and current advancements relevant to our research area.

A. UAVs in NTN-wireless communications

In the industrial revolution, from Industrial 3.0 to Industrial 4.0 and 5.0, the key enabling technologies are AI, data science, and machinery automation, which need to be constantly connected with low-latency communications. Researchers propose that UAVs can play a potential part in wireless communication networks due to their rapid on-demand deployment and mobility capability. Two of the use cases are discussed here in this section.

FIGURE 2. UAV-assisted wireless communications

1) Air-to-Air (A2A)

In parallel to the terrestrial wireless communication networks, drones can be deployed in the air to provide wireless networks to ground and air users. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the direct communication link between the Ground Users (GUs) and the BS affects the communication quality and connectivity. Fig. 2 illustrates the communication scenario where BS is providing coverage to the GUEs and AUEs.

In some cases, the GUEs do not have Line of Sight (LOS) links or access to connectivity. In that case, drones can relay the information between the GBS and GUEs. In drone-to-drone communication, the cellular spectrum can be reused, which is used for UL by the GUs [41]. However, the drones should be sufficiently at a higher altitude for interference mitigation. The propagating channel in A2A communications fundamentally depends upon the LOS alignment, trajectories, flight timings, and Doppler shifts [42]. In order to optimize the energy resource in the swarm of drones, a methodology has been proposed to follow one drone (leader) who will be responsible for trajectory design [43]. The same mechanism can be implemented in disastrous recovery situations or demand-based situations where the swarm of UAVs is required to provide connectivity. The AI technologies can help to optimize the energy on board [44], trajectory design, and LOS alignment [45]. A 3D elevation based on a two-cylinder reference model has been proposed for LOS alignment and is also capable of decoding single and double-bounced rays [46]. To understand the channel characteristics in UAV-enabled communications, a study on measurements using channel sounding technologies has been presented in [47]. In air-air, air-ground, and ground-ground wireless communications, the channel model is different in the wake of different characteristics, which results in mutual interference. Therefore, subchannel allocation combined with drone speed optimization has been proposed to maximize the system's sum rate [48]. Similarly, multipath interference has been studied in [49], and handover management for reducing interference has been presented in [50].

The propagation characteristics for UAVs depend on the altitude and environment. The measured data for the S-band radio propagation environment was studied in Hawaii and found reflection from the sea and large buildings [51]. Considering this scenario, a predictive model based on AI has been proposed, and a two-ray model has been considered for pathloss measurements [52], [53]. Recently, exploiting the advantages of UAVs over terrestrial networks, swarms of UAVs have been considered to present a virtual antenna array environment [54]. This kind of system model can be used for cooperative beamforming [55] and collaborative UAV tasks [56].

UAV communication's unique 3D propagation characteristics introduce significant security threats due to their dynamic and unpredictable signal behavior. The high mobility of UAVs and wide coverage capabilities expand the number of potential interception points, increasing the risk of eavesdropping and unauthorized access. Additionally, the 3D propagation environment makes UAV communication more susceptible to jamming and spoofing, resulting in loss of control, denial of service, or misdirection of the UAVs. However, the various altitudes and angles make their communication channels harder to predict and secure, which can be exploited to avoid unauthorized access, eavesdropping, and jamming. Similarly, high mobility introduces significant Doppler shifts

and frequency variations, which can be used to harden the communication channel, discussed later in detail in Section III.

2) Air-to-Ground (A2G)

One of the most important applications of UAVs was to enable wireless communications in remote areas by Google [22] and Facebook [57]. Prior to these two projects, UAV was tested in Lincoln Laboratory using laser technology for A2G payload communication [58]. They achieved high data rates; however, laser technology is not a reliable option for domestic wireless communications due to its high cost and complexity.

The low-cost solution to enable wireless communications is the utilization of terrestrial cellular networks and extending the coverage with the help of LAP UAVs [59]. In disaster-affected zones, terrestrial networks mostly fail to provide connectivity to wireless networks. Hence, UAVs are used to provide wireless connectivity to users in disaster zones by expanding the coverage [60]. In this work, LAP UAVs are used to maximize coverage with minimum energy consumption to improve the flight time of the UAV. Despite improving coverage, the jitter effect due to airflow is also present due to the lack of fixed infrastructure. This jitter effect affects the antenna or antenna array alignment and so as beamforming [61]. *A Pathloss model for A2G channel has been discussed based on the experimental data in suburban environment [62]. A multi-layer UAV architecture has been presented in [63] to address challenges such as energy consumption, latency, and interference. Another use case where UAVs provide connectivity to maritime areas has been presented in [64] and analyzed the outage probability due to the shores.*

Due to their unique characteristics, such as LOS transmission, high mobility, and variable propagation environments, A2G communications channels are highly relevant to the study and application of PLS. These properties present both challenges and opportunities for securing A2G communications using PLS techniques. By exploiting the inherent physical properties of the channel, it is possible to enhance the security of A2G communications against eavesdropping, jamming, and other security threats [32]. *A few major vulnerabilities and corrective measures in UAV communications have been presented covering the authentication and PLS in [65]. Similarly, a comprehensive study on the cryptographic methods in UAV communications focusing on ground control station links, UAV-to-UAV, and UAV traffic management links has been presented in [66]. However, both [65] and [66] primarily address high-layer security, with limited emphasis on PLS.*

Considering the A2G scenarios, techniques such as beamforming and Artificial Noise (AN) can be used to degrade the quality of the signal received by an eavesdropper while maintaining the signal quality for the intended receiver [67].

Similarly, based on the unique characteristics of the A2G channels, the random variations in Channel State Information (CSI) can be exploited to generate secure cryptographic keys between legitimate users.

3) Ground-to-Air (G2A)

Ground-to-air (G2A) communication channels enable reliable data exchange between terrestrial systems and airborne platforms such as aircraft, UAVs, and HAPs. These channels operate under unique propagation conditions characterized by varying altitude, mobility, and atmospheric influences, making their modeling and optimization a complex yet exciting area of research. The interesting features of G2A are its dynamic nature, such as multipath propagation, Doppler shifts, and LOS variability. For instance, considering the factors, the feasibility of the G2A network and the coverage issues have been analyzed [68]. Furthermore, significant challenges exist, including signal attenuation due to atmospheric absorption, interference management in crowded airspaces, and the need for robust channel models that can adapt to rapid changes in topology and environmental conditions. Moreover, ensuring secure and low-latency communications in such scenarios requires overcoming these obstacles while adhering to stringent safety and regulatory standards.

Ultraviolet frequencies are considered for G2A communications in UAV systems because of their distinctive features, such as scattering capability, high security, atmospheric transparency, and resistance to radio frequency interference. However, their application is generally limited to LAPs due to the high attenuation associated with UV signals [69]. The long-distance communications in G2A experience time-varying dispersions due to ionospheric medium, which has been analyzed, and optimal frequency selection has been proposed in [70]. Considering challenges related to site selection and antenna selection for mission planning, an AI algorithm based on genetic algorithm optimization has been studied to optimize high-frequency communications in [71].

Communications between airborne platforms and ground stations demand robust interference resistance, higher data rates, and high reliability. However, low elevation angles often introduce multipath effects, significantly impacting the performance of the communications link. To address this challenge, a precoding scheme exploring the channel block diagonalization has been proposed in [72], enabling the parallel utilization of sub-channels to ensure high reliability. To enhance link reliability, a machine learning-based tracking mechanism has been proposed in [73], while semantic communication techniques have been explored in [74] to improve data rates.

Five critical aspects are taken into consideration, with the contributions to the discussed use cases summarized in Table 3. These aspects include A2A, A2G, G2A, security and the integration of UAVs in cooperative networks.

The researcher provides balanced attention to these areas, highlighting their potential applications and challenges. However, despite advancements in UAV technology, security concerns remain a significant challenge due to inherent constraints such as weight and power limitations. These limitations underline the need for more robust and efficient solutions to address security vulnerabilities effectively. The conventional security methods face challenges in A2A and A2G communication due to the unique characteristics of the airborne environment, such as high mobility, open airspace, and resource constraints. Researchers are moving towards more specialized and adaptive security approaches to address these challenges effectively. Techniques like PLS, lightweight cryptography, adaptive security protocols, and emerging technologies like Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) and machine learning offer promising solutions for ensuring secure and reliable UAV communications in the future.

II. Potential UAV Solutions

The main advantage of UAV as a BS over terrestrial wireless networks is its high dynamic stability due to maneuverability, which allows us to provide LOS with rigorous energy constraints and a unique propagation environment. The maneuverability of UAVs affects the wireless channels that can be utilized to enhance the PLS (PLS), which has been discussed in more detail in [77]. Considering these concepts, cooperative communication through mobile UAVs offers more security, especially in URLLC in 5G and beyond [78]. The potential UAV solution in PLS is discussed in the following subsections.

A. Impact of Pathloss

The Pathloss Models (PMs) in terrestrial wireless networks are well-established, while in contrast, the UAV propagation environment is unique, with barely any available models. This uniqueness of the propagation environment makes it special, having a direct impact on the user's requirements. The UAV-enabled wireless communications propagation model can be categorized into three sub-parts: BS to UAV, UAV to GU, and UAV to UAV. In these three cases, the impact on system-level performance for Device-to-Device (D2D) communications, coverage, and Ad-Hoc networks has been discussed in [79]. The BS to UAV case has been tested for a PM exploiting 700-900 MHz LTE bands with 100 - 150 meters UAV altitude [80]. These measurements have been carried out in the suburban area of west Melbourne, Australia, where tree and building heights are up to 40m and 12m, respectively. They considered the LOS scenario with a fixed antenna facing downward, which can eventually affect the outage rate. In [81], the authors considered more realistic configurable antennas to enhance the coverage, and the channel model has been discussed. However, when UAVs are looking for the nearest association, it introduces interference to the nearest BS and results in low throughput to GUs.

TABLE 3. UAVs in wireless communications

Paper	Contribution	A2A	A2G	G2A	Security	Cooperation in UAVs
[65]	Vulnerabilities and countermeasures for UAV security	No discussion on the use cases	No discussion on the use cases	No discussion on the use cases	higher layer, limited emphasis on PLS	×
[66]	Cryptographic methods in UAVs	✓	ground control station has been taken into consideration, not the communication link to GUs	Command and Control link has been considered	higher layer, limited emphasis on PLS	×
[63]	Energy consumption, low-latency, and interference	✓	✓	✓	×	Partially discussed
[64]	Extending the coverage and providing connectivity to maritime areas through tethered drone	×	Air-to-sea has been considered	✓	×	×
[32]	Physical layer security in UAV communication	✓	✓	×	Keyless approaches have been discussed	✓
[41]	Used the same UL band for the GUs for UAV-to-UAV communications	✓	×	×	Partially discussed	×
[53]	Prediction model based received signal strength using machine learning	✓	×	×	×	Partially discussed for the different altitude maintenance of UAVs
[75]	Secrecy outage probability has been derived	Securing the UAV network in the air	×	×	Secrecy outage probability and average secret capacity have been discussed	Partially discussed
[76]	Optimal secure routing technique has been proposed called as modified hunter prey optimization	✓	✓	×	×	
[55]	Anti-jamming and optimization of beamforming parameter and UAV's altitude	Space-to-Air and A2A have been discussed	Space-to-Ground and A2G have been discussed	Partially discussed	Two-stage anti-jamming scheme, keyless approach	For Beamforming purposes

The interference caused by the UAVs to the non-serving BS and GUs is decreased, and overall QoE is increased by the low energy allocation algorithm [82]. Another important use case is to enable wireless communications in disaster and emergency situations in urban areas. The same use case has been considered for uplink and downlink channel modeling using the Winner II model, which already accommodates the LOS and NLOS conditions [83]. They also considered the impact of UAV altitude, height of the buildings, and distance between transmitter and receiver on the PM. The propagation environment in various terrains is different, and in mountain

areas where terrains are sporadic, channel modeling becomes very difficult in these situations. This situation has been taken into consideration, and the generic free space PM is modified with a 2-ray model [84].

In 6G, we aim to have a Space-Air-Ground-Sea Integrated Network (SAGSIN). Hence, the channel model is necessarily non-stationary and consistent as well, which is, of course, a challenging task to implement, especially in more dynamic and changing environments like bullet trains, UAVs and vehicles, etc. These types of cases have been discussed in detail for mmwave-THz MIMO systems [85]. Fig. 3 represents

FIGURE 3. Space and air integrated networks

different components and platforms in a communication network, i.e., the first layer depicts the constellation of satellites, followed by the second layer containing HAP. The third layer includes LAP, while the fourth layer comprises GUs and ground BSs. The fifth and final layer represents ocean and underwater communication. LAP and HAP can serve users in remote areas, disaster recovery areas, or event-specific situations, whereas HAP and satellites can integrate to provide connectivity to ocean and underwater users. Furthermore, these platforms can also be used to provide links between space and ground to provide low-latency communications and improve coverage. This layered structure highlights the diverse and comprehensive nature of modern communication networks to provide seamless connectivity and capable of providing backhaul support. Modeling on pathloss effects on UAV communication signal has been studied in [86] while [87] proposed a HAP-reserved architecture to link the communication from ground to space. A comprehensive table of channel models in UAV-enabled communications is given in Table III of the survey paper [88]. A summary and comparison of a few survey papers is given in Table 4.

While pathloss establishes the baseline signal attenuation over distance, shadowing and fading introduce additional complexities that degrade communication reliability. Shadowing arises from environmental obstructions, leading to unpredictable signal variations, while fading is caused by multipath effects and is influenced by mobility and dynamic environments. Together, these phenomena impact the effective

channel quality and pose challenges for reliable communication and PLS in UAV-enabled NTN scenarios. In HAP-UAV or UAV-UAV, channels follow shadowed Rician or Nakagami-m fading for small-scale fading [89], while the HAP-satellite link doesn't experience small-scale fading and follows the free space model [90]. The air-satellite channel models have been developed and discussed in detail in [91], [92]. However, the channels become different in a UAV-to-ground environment. The 3D models have been developed to account for UAV altitude and mobility, as well as the presence of NLOS conditions caused by obstructions such as terrain or buildings [31], [46]. The pathloss model and fast fading model have been discussed for improvement of PLS against hybrid wireless attacks in [93]. Similarly, a propagation model has been developed and discussed for integrated TNs and NTNs in [94], and security aspects have been explored in [95].

Despite the advancements in NTN channel models, significant challenges require consideration. One major issue is the highly dynamic nature of UAV communication, which leads to varying propagation distances and shadowing effects. Additionally, high-frequency bands, such as mmwave and THz, exhibit greater susceptibility to attenuation, which complicates the design of reliable NTN communication systems [96]. A few intelligent approaches, such as altitude-aware path loss models, statistical shadowing frameworks, and MIMO-based solutions, have been explored to address these challenges. However, their impact on PLS, particularly regarding SKG and robust transmission, highlights the need

for further research into adaptive and environment-aware solutions.

In UAV communication, pathloss significantly impacts the effectiveness of PLS techniques, which rely on exploiting the physical characteristics of wireless channels to secure communication. Pathloss affects the secrecy capacity, which is the maximum rate at which secure communication can occur based on the signal quality difference between legitimate receivers and eavesdroppers. High pathloss can reduce the SNR for both the legitimate receiver and eavesdropper [97]. However, if the legitimate receiver is closer to the transmitter, creating a significant difference in pathloss, it can enhance secrecy capacity and improve the effectiveness of PLS [98]. Techniques such as AN generation, which degrades the eavesdropper's signal, can be impacted by pathloss. While a high pathloss might weaken both the legitimate signal and the AN, strategic deployment can still ensure that noise primarily affects distant eavesdroppers, preserving communication quality for the legitimate receiver. PLS techniques also utilize channel fading and diversity by employing beamforming and cooperative diversity methods to optimize signal quality for legitimate users while minimizing it for eavesdroppers [99]. Increased pathloss can challenge these techniques by reducing coherence and the ability to maintain high secrecy capacity, though significant pathloss differences across various communication paths can still enhance security. Similarly, key generation based on channel characteristics, such as signal strength and phase, can be affected by a high pathloss. While degraded signal quality may reduce key precision, notable pathloss differences between the legitimate and eavesdropper's channels can still facilitate secure key generation. To address the impact of pathloss on PLS, adaptive strategies such as dynamic power control, adaptive beamforming, mobility-based optimization, frequency selection and hopping, and relay or cooperative communication techniques can be employed. These methods help maintain optimal SNR, minimize pathloss, enhance secrecy capacity, and improve overall communication security and reliability in dynamic UAV environments.

B. Energy Efficiency (EE)

Despite the numerous advantages of wireless communication networks, UAVs face several limitations, such as Size, Weight, and Power, collectively known as SWaP. It is evident that factors like weight, size, and payload during communication can significantly impact the UAV's power reserves [106]. One approach to extending the flight time of UAVs for wireless communication in certain areas is the use of tethered UAVs. These tethered UAVs can provide wireless connectivity, while other UAVs are assigned tasks such as video transmission [107]. However, tethering affects the UAV's maneuverability, making it essential to optimize power consumption for information signal transmission. Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transfer (SWIPT) is employed to enhance energy efficiency

in NOMA-based D2D communication networks [108]. L. Amorosi *et al.* have proposed an energy-efficient solution to provide 5G coverage in rural areas [109]. They addressed challenges such as rural coverage, optimal ground station selection for UAV recharging, and managing energy from solar panels. The mathematical representation of battery backup and energy levels can be expressed as:

$$SBL_t = SBL_{t-1} + SP_t - URE_t, \quad (1)$$

where, SBL_t is the battery level at a ground station where the UAV can recharge itself at a time t , SBL_{t-1} is the battery level at ground station $t-1$, SP_t is the energy from a solar panel at time t , and URE_t is the recharging energy of UAV at time t . Similarly, the equation of energy level with a UAV perspective is also given:

$$UEL_t = UEL_{t-1} + URR_t - UCE_t, \quad (2)$$

where UEL_t and UEL_{t-1} represent the energy level at UAV at time t and $t-1$, respectively, while URR_t and UCE_t represents recharge rate and consumption rate at time t , respectively.

An energy-efficient 5G-enabled opportunistic network where Flight Control System (FCS) is offloaded at the network edge by exploiting Multiple access Edge Computing (MEC) allows the autonomous flight of UAVs using 5G networks and real-time energy usage optimization [110]. Energy conservation at different layers and cross-layers of the communication networks in four phases of UAV communication, i.e., idle mode, node selection mode, path selection mode, and coordination mode, are discussed [104]. These concepts of UAVs allow us to enable wireless communications in remote and disaster areas with less energy consumption and in a more efficient way where UAVs take advantage of the terrestrial networks.

Energy-efficient UAVs play an essential role in enhancing PLS by supporting extended operational lifespan, optimized power allocation, and sustained implementation of security measures. Efficient energy use allows UAVs to operate longer, ensuring secure communication over extended missions, which is crucial for real-time monitoring and surveillance tasks. By optimizing power allocation, energy-efficient UAVs can direct more power toward PLS techniques, such as dynamic power control, adaptive beamforming, and AN generation, to enhance the SNR for legitimate receivers while minimizing the chance of eavesdropping. This energy efficiency also supports advanced security measures like cooperative communication and relay, which create complex signal paths, making interception difficult. Furthermore, UAVs have the capability to adjust their positions and routing paths to optimize communication channels, minimize pathloss, and maximize secrecy capacity by frequency hopping and adaptive frequency selection, reducing interception risks. With the efficient balancing of energy consumption and security needs, UAVs can sustain strong and secure communication links, providing resilience against eavesdropping and en-

TABLE 4. Comparison of survey papers on UAVs-enable communication

Paper	PLM	EE	PLS	Contribution	A2A	A2G	Swarm
[88]	✓	×	×	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A2G Channel, • Survey of realistic data from Channel sounder, • Measurement from exploring other IEEE 802.11 protocols in urban, suburban, rural, and hilly areas 	×	✓	×
[85]	✓	Discussed Partially Discussed	×	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mathematical and Physical definition of Channel consistency and non-stationary channels • Comprehensive comparison of existing and proposed channel models (in point 1.) 	Partially Dis- cussed	discussed	Partially Dis- cussed
[100]	✓	Partially Discussed	Partially Dis- cussed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beamforming is discussed in detail for mmwave-UAV-enabled wireless communications • Basic issues are discussed in cellular-connected UAV-mmwave and UAV-mmwave ad hoc networks 	✓	✓	✓
[101]	Partially Dis- cussed	✓	×	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level overview of Aerial Radio Access networks • Propagation environment, system mobility, and energy consumption are discussed 	Partially Dis- cussed	✓	✓
[35]	×	×	Stack security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Characterization and potential challenges in SAGSIN • Security threats, attacks and counteracts in SAGSIN 	Partially Dis- cussed	✓	×
[102]	✓	✓	Network Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review based on mobility in mmwave communications • Channel models and future directions in V2X, SAGNIS, and high-speed trains are discussed 	×	✓	×
[103]	✓	✓	✓	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review of fundamental channel models for Cell-Free massive MIMO • Precoding and detection strategies of uplink and downlink in Cell-Free massive MIMO • Cell Free concept in UAV using RIS and NOMA 	×	✓	×
[104]	×	✓	×	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topologies in UAV-enable wireless communications and topology changes in a run-time environment • Types of seamless handover • EE in protocols on each layer of UAV communication model 	✓	✓	✓
[105]	✓	✓	×	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Channel models, UAV deployment, and trajectory optimization • Resources Allocation and optimization problems 	✓	✓	Partially Dis- cussed

hancing the overall reliability of UAV-NTN communication networks.

C. Need of Physical Layer Security

NTNs are bridging the gaps by enabling seamless global ubiquitous connectivity across borders, oceans, and skies, meeting the needs of industries such as aviation, maritime, and autonomous systems. By complementing terrestrial networks, NTNs address the growing demand for reliable and high-quality communication, laying the foundation for

future innovations and digital inclusion. Given the critical role of NTNs, safeguarding the confidentiality and integrity of transmitted information becomes crucial. The broadcast nature of NTN communication channels, coverage, and mobility significantly increases the risk of eavesdropping, signal jamming, and data interception. Considering these characteristics of NTN, traditional approaches are less effective due to infrastructure-based security. PLS exploits the randomness of wireless channels, such as fading, noise, and Doppler effects, to secure communication at the physical

layer without relying on computational overhead or shared secrets. This makes PLS particularly suited for NTN and UAV applications, providing lightweight, adaptive, and scalable security solutions capable of operating in dynamic environments while ensuring low latency and energy-efficient secure communication. PLS is especially effective in dynamic NTN environments, where rapid mobility and changing topologies make conventional security approaches less practical. Thus, PLS not only enhances the security and reliability of NTNs but also ensures their ability to meet the demands of seamless and secure global communication, making it a foundation for the future of NTN systems [111].

Despite the significant advantages of PLS over traditional cryptographic measures, several challenges persist, affecting its widespread adoption. One notable challenge lies in the assumptions regarding the eavesdropper's channel. These assumptions often rely on idealized or overly simplistic models that may not align with practical scenarios, where Eve's channel characteristics are typically unknown or highly dynamic. Furthermore, much of the foundational work in PLS is rooted in asymptotic information theory, focusing on bounds and performance metrics under infinite block lengths. This approach often neglects practical constraints, such as finite block lengths and real-world implementation complexities, which are critical for real-time applications. Another challenge is the nascent state of PLS in terms of experimental validation and measurement. While theoretical advancements have been substantial, translating these concepts into practical systems remains in its infancy. Few researchers are actively exploring measurement and testing frameworks for PLS. For instance, works like [112] and [113] have made some developments in testing SKG techniques in different environments and use cases, providing valuable insights into the feasibility and performance of PLS in real-world conditions. However, the need is to develop standardized testing methodologies and establish benchmarks to bridge the gap between theory and practice in PLS.

III. Physical Layer Security

The three main parts of wireless communications security are confidentiality, integrity, and availability, known as the CIA Triad, which can be portrayed over the communication, hardware, and software plane. As shown in Fig. 4, communication is more concerned with the confidentiality and integrity of information of legitimate users. Confidentiality is a consolidated constituent of privacy [114], [115], and the purpose is not to make legitimate users' information available to unauthorized users. Confidentiality can be ensured by applying a strategic approach where modification in input data is subject to encryption that is aligned with time relevance. This means that any changes made to sensitive information are immediately encrypted, ensuring that the data remains secure and confidential even as it is modified. Time relevance plays a crucial role by ensuring that encryption processes and confidentiality measures are applied correctly, such as during

data transmission or when updates occur. This relevance can be maintained through mechanisms such as logging (which tracks access and changes in real-time), monitoring connections (to detect unauthorized access), and managing the association or de-association of data with specific users or sessions. Furthermore, randomizing the order in which data is processed or accessed can add an additional layer of protection by making unauthorized pattern detection and inference more difficult. Together, these elements maintain data confidentiality by ensuring it is encrypted and secure throughout its lifecycle, only accessible to authorized entities at appropriate times. At the same time, the information needs to be made available to legitimate users over the life span of the communication link, which can only be possible with integrity [116], [117]. The availability is ensured by the access server by authorization of users, while integrity is responsible for data validation, backup for the life cycle, and audit trails. Many approaches have been used and proposed on the different layers of the OSI layers so far. However, wireless communications infrastructure over the UEs is uncertain, and the only option is to secure the information by securing the communication link over the physical layer. Furthermore, in wireless communications, the physical layer is the first layer to exploit the random channel gain, and due to the broadcast nature, the information becomes more susceptible to eavesdroppers. These two reasons make the PLS signify over the other higher layers of the OSI model.

To ensure PLS in wireless communications, researchers have contributed and proposed many technologies and techniques since Shannon and Weaver gave a concrete information-theoretic approach for secure wireless communications in 1948 [118], [119]. This model gives two main things: (i) the highest compression rate that can be achieved without compromising the original data, and (ii) the highest possible data transfer could be achieved for a given source. It is considered to be the basis for all the security models, as this article introduces a new approach toward security. Shannon and Weaver's model categorized wireless communications into three levels.

- 1) **Technical Problem:** How accurately can the symbols be transmitted?
- 2) **Semantic Problem:** How precisely do the transmitted symbols convey the desired meaning?
- 3) **Effectiveness Problem:** How effectively does the received meaning affect conduct in the desired way?

This explanation is given by Weaver of Shannon's mathematical theory of communications and is ostensibly appropriate to the technical problem only, i.e., accuracy problem. However, it provides significant contributions to semantic and effectiveness problems. Weaver pursued the explanation and broadened the scope of information theory, while Shannon developed a theoretical framework for security based on organized complexity. In contrast to Wiener's theory based on disorganized complexity [120], Shannon used prob-

FIGURE 4. CIA triad in communications

ability to quantify information, entropy, and communication channel capacity, while Wiener applied probability in the study of stochastic processes, noise, and filtering. Their works are foundational to information theory and heavily rely on probabilistic methods to model and solve problems in communication, signal processing, and system control. Thus, it's more accurate to say that both theories have a direct relationship with probability. However, both theories are closely related and solve communications and security problems. Presently, in 5G communications standards, the researchers have almost achieved the Shannon capacity and are considering the semantic and effectiveness problems in the cyber-physical systems to present wireless communications beyond Shannon [121].

Security concerns in communication systems were fundamentally considered by Shannon, who applied an information-theoretic approach to the problem [119]. His model involved a legitimate transmitter (Alice), a legitimate receiver (Bob), and an eavesdropper (Eve), whom he referred to as an "enemy," all sharing a noiseless channel, which he later extended to noisy channels. However, Shannon's work focused on theoretical limits rather than specific communication layers. Building on this foundation, Aaron D. Wyner was the first to explicitly consider the PLS in 1975 and introduced the wiretap channel model, where Alice, Bob, and Eve communicated over noisy channels [122]. This model, which assumed discrete memoryless channels for both Bob and Eve, demonstrated that secure communication could be achieved at the physical layer by exploiting the noise properties of the channels. If Eve's channel was noisier than Bob's, secrecy capacity will be greater than zero which means Alice could transmit data securely without relying on cryptographic techniques, marking the foundation of PLS.

Presenting an overall picture, the wireless security systems could be categorized in conventional cryptography, introduced by Shannon [118], and physical layer-based security. In Shannon's model, secure key generation and exchange between legitimate users were considered under the assumption of both noiseless and noisy channels. Another

assumption was that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) received by legitimate users (Bob) was better than that received by an eavesdropper (Eve). In this setup, the key was assumed to be valid for the entire communication session, which introduced the risk of Eve gaining knowledge of the key, potentially compromising secrecy. In contrast, Wyner's wiretap model accounted for channel noise and assumed that the SNR at the eavesdropper was worse than at the legitimate receiver [122]. This model demonstrated that secure communication could be achieved without key exchange by exploiting physical layer characteristics, such as noise and channel coding. As a result, keyless PLS emerged, where security is ensured through bit-level or symbol-level channel coding, removing the need for traditional cryptographic key exchanges [123]. In contribution toward keyless PLS, the scientific community proposed channel adaptation-based security to leverage the independent fluctuations and fading effects experienced by legitimate and illegitimate users, turning these characteristics to the advantage of the legitimate users [124]. Over the past decade, researchers have also explored the addition of AN to the information signal to create interference for eavesdroppers, further enhancing security [125]. Both techniques (channel adaptation and AN addition) can be applied across the temporal, frequency, and spatial domains. Keyless PLS offers significant advantages: it eliminates the need for secret cryptographic keys and complex key exchange mechanisms, shifts most of the processing burden to the transmitter, and is compatible with both Time Division Duplexing (TDD) and Frequency Division Duplexing (FDD) systems.

The keyless PLS approach ensures secrecy in case of less SNR at Eve compared to legitimate users and is also sensitive to channel errors. Furthermore, the energy consumption is higher in channel adaptation and the addition of AN in the case of beamforming/ precoding. Most of the processing is carried out at BS, but UAVs have energy limitations if used as a BS. So, the better option is to utilize common resources among legitimate users and ensure secrecy. It has been found that the transmitter and receiver could exploit the channel to generate their own secret keys, as the channel is the same, so

it is assumed that the secret keys would also be the same but depends on the reciprocity and fluctuations in the common stochastic channel. Another concept of QKD is given in [126], in which keys are generated as a random sequence of bits through the classical information and distributed among the legitimate users over the quantum channels. Both approaches are discussed and illustrated in Fig. 8. This approach is not feasible in UAV networks because of the complex infrastructure-based security, which makes this topic out of the scope of this article. The merits and demerits of keyless and key-based PLS are given in Table 5.

TABLE 5. Merits and demerits of keyless and key-based PLS

Category	Keyless PLS	Key-based PLS
Merits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perfect Secrecy can be achieved • A significant part of processing is done at Transmitter • Can be used in TDD and FDD • There is no need to share the secret keys 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secret keys are generated individually, and there is no need for distribution • Maintain secrecy regardless of the Eve SNR • Transmitter and Receiver both ensure PLS • Provide authentication
Demerits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only feasible when SNR of the legitimate user is higher than Eve's SNR • Energy consumption is higher • Sensitive to channel errors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key length is limited; thus, perfect secrecy is hard to achieve • Processing power at both ends is required • Sensitive to quantization errors • TDD is the limitation

Prior to going into a comprehensive discussion of PLS, basic types of illegitimate users and secrecy metrics need to be discussed for a better understanding of the reader. The illegitimate user, in this case, could be an active eavesdropper or passive eavesdropper. The **active eavesdropper** is the one having the capability to observe and modify the contents, while the **passive eavesdropper** has the capability of observation only. Hence, identifying passive eavesdroppers is difficult compared to active eavesdroppers.

Assume that the k number of Alice's message bits as w^k , enciphered into codeword X^n transmitted over the channel \mathbf{H} , where n represents codeword symbols, and $X^n = (X(1), \dots, X(n))$. Bob and Eve receive $Y^n = (Y(1), \dots, Y(n))$, and $Z^n = (Z(1), \dots, Z(n))$. The signal received by Bob and Eve can be written as $Y(i) =$

$\mathbf{H}_{ab}X(i) + \mathbf{N}_b$, and $Z(i) = \mathbf{H}_{ae}X(i) + \mathbf{N}_e$, respectively, for $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. Where \mathbf{H}_{ab} , and \mathbf{H}_{ae} represent the common channel between Alice and Bob and Alice and Eve, while \mathbf{N}_b , and \mathbf{N}_e respectively, represent noise at Bob and Eve. *The assumed model is illustrated in Fig. 5, which provides a graphical representation of Wyner's wiretap model. According to this model, there is no need to encrypt the message if the secrecy capacity is greater than zero. Mathematically, this condition holds when Z is degraded relative to Y , satisfying the necessary and sufficient condition..*

FIGURE 5. Underlying wiretap model

1) Secrecy Metrics

Secrecy metrics are important for assessing the effectiveness of securing sensitive information against eavesdropping through quantitative framework for evaluating the level of achievable secrecy in PLS. These metrics support in validation of methods particularly in scenarios where the communication environment and channel characteristics play a critical role. In the following subsections, we discussed the secrecy metrics and visually summarized in the second half of Fig. 6.

Secrecy Rate

According to Shannon's information theory, the secrecy rate equals the maximum data compression rate with which communication can be carried out effectively. Assume W is the random variable representing data, and n is the number of codeword symbols. The entropy defines the compression rate, i.e., $H(W)$. The mathematical representation is given as follows:

$$R_s = H(W)/n. \quad (3)$$

The foundational ideas related to the secrecy rate are rooted in Shannon's work to achieve perfect secrecy. However, the concept of secrecy rate as it is understood today was formally introduced by Wyner in 1975 [122] for wiretap channels and extended to the Gaussian wiretap in [127]. It is the closest value to the highest difference between the legitimate user's achievable rate and the illegitimate user's achievable rate, sometimes called the supremum of the difference. The mathematical representation is as follows.

$$R_s = [R_i - R_e]^+, \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 6. PLS classification and secrecy metrics

where R_s, R_i , and R_e are the secrecy rate, the achievable rate at legitimate users, and the achievable rate at illegitimate users, respectively. The goal of PLS is to maximize this difference or R_s , which can be represented mathematically as $\max(\sum R_s)$. In [128], an ergodic secrecy rate (the average ability to securely transmit over fading channels) has been derived for RIS-aided NTN secure THz communications. The satellite link through cooperative UAV communication has been discussed, and the ergodic secrecy rate has been derived in [129].

Secrecy Outage Probability (SOP)

Secret Outage Probability (SOP) is defined as the probability of secrecy rate R_s is less than the desired secrecy threshold, mathematically can be written as [130]:

$$SOP = P(R_s < R_{req}), \quad (5)$$

where, R_{req} is the desired secrecy rate at the legitimate user, and $P(\cdot)$ represents the Probability Distribution Function (PDF). In NTN, SOP has been derived for an environment where UAV has been used to provide a communications link to underwater-RIS in [131].

Secrecy throughput

Secrecy Throughput (ST) is the term used in PLS, representing the maximum achievable SR in practical environments.

$$R_s^T = \max(R_s). \quad (6)$$

Security Gap

Security gap is defined as the difference between the SNR at the legitimate user and the SNR at the eavesdropper. Mathematically, the security gap can be represented as:

$$S_g = SNR_l - SNR_e. \quad (7)$$

Equivocation-based metrics

Shannon initially developed the equivocation-based metrics, which were later on considered by Wyner to measure the amount of confusion and to what extent the wiretapper could exist. These measurements can be calculated from the information signal through the posterior entropy. The supreme value of equivocation tends to be perfect secrecy. The maximum fractional equivocation can be written as a piecewise function, given as follows.

$$\Delta = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } R_e \leq R_b - R_s \\ (R_b - R_e)/R_s & \text{if } R_b - R_s < R_e < R_b \\ 0 & \text{if } R_b \leq R_e \end{cases}, \quad (8)$$

where R_b is the achievable rate at Bob.

Secret Key Rate (SKR)

The secret key rate is the number of secret key-bits generated per unit time. A high secret key rate without compromising the data rate of legitimate users is considered favorable for security enhancement.

$$R_{key} = \frac{K_n}{T}, \quad (9)$$

where K_n is number of bits generated during time T (bits per second). In some cases, it is also defined as *the number of secret bits per sample of the considered attribute (bits per sample)*. The KGR can be influenced by various factors, such as computational resources and the efficiency of an algorithm.

Key Mismatch Probability (KMP)

The probability of the secret keys on which both legitimate users do not agree is called Key Mismatch Probability (KMP). The KMP can also be calculated from the Key Agreement Probability (KAP) by subtracting KAP from 1. When the bits in the secret key generated at both nodes do not match, they will also be considered mismatch keys.

$$P_{mm} = \frac{B_{mm}}{K_n}, \quad (10)$$

where B_{mm} is the number of mismatched bits in secret keys generated by Bob and Alice.

Key Randomness

Randomness in the secret keys is important; the more randomness in the keys, the better the encryption. Most of the literature on Secret Key Generation (SKG) using Channel State Information (CSI) is based on randomizing seeds in programming tools like Matlab. Furthermore, Statistical Test Suite has been used to generate random or pseudo-random numbers, specifying a set of statistical tests for randomness. The National Institute of Standard Technology (NIST) has also been considered in the literature and is available to the public as a source of randomness; it also provides a suite for randomness tests. NIST uses the multiple available independent commercial sources of randomness. NIST was founded in 1901, contributing to technology through research and standardization. In 1977, the Data Encryption Standard (DES) was made available to the public and presented in [132]. Later on, Advanced Encryption Standard algorithms were made public [133], and key randomness was ensured through different algorithms [134].

Channel Resolvability-Based Metrics

The comparative performance analysis of finding the minimum rate using the ergodicity of the channel equals the length of the uniform random numbers and can estimate the desired channel distribution is considered as channel resolvability-based metrics.

Before delving into the detailed discussion of PLS classification, it is essential to provide a summarized overview of the secrecy metrics and classification. This overview is encapsulated in Fig. 6, which visually represents the core elements involved in PLS. Fig. 6 systematically categorizes the various secrecy metrics, providing a clear and concise framework that aids in understanding the complex landscape

of PLS. This preliminary summary sets the stage for a more in-depth exploration of the classification methodologies and their respective implications in securing physical layers.

A. Information Theoretic Approach

Information theory is important in wireless communication systems, especially in PLS. In information theory, the information content is represented by a random variable \mathbf{X} with discrete sample space $X \triangleq \{1, \dots, x\}$, and the message signal observed at eavesdropper is considered as random variable \mathbf{Z}^n , where n is the number of symbols in sample space Z . In information theory, secrecy can be defined as the mutual information between legitimate and illegitimate users. For simplicity, one legitimate receiver and one eavesdropper are considered; hence, secrecy is $I(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Z}^n)$, where $I(\cdot)$ represents the mutual information. In **Perfect Secrecy**, the R_s is exactly matching the R_i (in Eq. 4) and mutual information is zero, i.e.,

$$I(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Z}^n) = 0, \forall x \in X \wedge \forall z^n \in Z^n, \quad (11)$$

This information-theoretic approach guarantees the perfect secrecy of the legitimate user incurious of the distribution of the random source. Nevertheless, the information leakage was formalized by Wyner [122] i.e.,

$$I(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Z}^n) \frac{1}{n} \leq \varepsilon, \quad (12)$$

where ε is greater than zero; however, very small. The factor $\frac{1}{n}$ in the term in Eq. 12 is the leakage rate of the information bits [135]. Considering this weak secrecy, **strong secrecy** has been introduced by Moore and Simmons [136] and further signified by Maurer and Wolf [137]. In these papers, the *rate of leakage information*, i.e., $\frac{1}{n}$, is incorporated in *amount of leakage information* as a measure of secrecy. Mathematically it can be represented as,

$$I(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Z}^n) \leq \varepsilon, \quad (13)$$

Now, the strong secrecy is dependent on the distribution of the random source, which leads to the possibility of indigent protection of a few unlikely information messages due to low probability and high relative entropy. The **semantic secrecy** can guarantee strong secrecy regardless of the message distribution. Mathematically, it can be written as:

$$\max(I(\mathbf{X}; \mathbf{Z}^n)) \leq \varepsilon, \forall x \in X \wedge \forall z^n \in Z^n \quad (14)$$

The term "Semantic Secrecy" was first introduced by Smith on securing the data for banking applications [138], and statistical interpretations are given in [139] by the name of **computational secrecy**. In the information-theoretic perspective, semantic secrecy is defined and modeled for multi-bit hiding commitments with an open question on reverse implications [140]. Semantic secrecy is complicated to apply to a code; however, the same results can be achieved with distinguishing secrecy [141], which was first proved

by considering equiprobable messages [142]. The relation among distinguishing secrecy, strong secrecy, and Kullback-Leibler-Differential Privacy are related through a multiplicative constant [143]. This relation is derived from anonymous communication privacy with the conception of Receiver-Message Linkability (RML). The authors considered one transmitter and two receivers in the presence of an adversary with the memoryless discrete broadcast channel. Furthermore, the rate region can also be defined based on the secrecy rates [144]. *Recently, a new concept of secrecy pressure has been introduced in [145], presenting an evaluation of the security level of the environment where the legitimate link exists, independent of the eavesdropper's location. This metric can also be visualized as a secrecy map. The authors in [145] represents the secrecy pressure mathematically as:*

$$P_{\text{sec}} = \frac{1}{A_S} \iint_S C_{\text{sec}} dx dy \quad (15)$$

where A_S represents the area of surface and C_{sec} is the secrecy capacity, i.e., $C_{\text{sec}} = [C_i - C_e]^+$ in reference to Eq. 4. This equation can be modified for UAV communications where a 3D model is applicable. For instance, the area will be extended to spherical volume, and the integration will be extended from 2D to 3D [146].

Recently, information-theoretic approaches have been considered in amalgamation with game-theoretic approaches. Makan *et al.* presented an information-theoretic game-theoretic approach for PLS in UAV communications [147]. They have considered two legitimate users, i.e., Alice and Bob. Alice sends a private message correlated with a non-private message in the first half of the communications and then suddenly starts sending another one correlated to the previously sent non-private message. Game theory, i.e., non-cooperative games, is used for the optimal power and energy values, coverage, and coordinate controls. It can also be used in UAVs to find the best altitude, coverage, and optimal power.

The challenging task in information-theoretic-based PLS is characterizing the achievable-rates region, which is even more difficult in Memoryless State-Dependent Broadcast Channels (MSDBC), even with feedback [148]. Recently, this issue has been addressed through joint sensing. However, in UAV communications, sensing will somehow affect communication performance. Hence, an efficient system must be made to characterize capacity regions better.

B. Resource Allocation

Resource allocation in wireless communications refers to the process of assigning available resources, such as bandwidth, power, time slots, and antenna resources to users or devices in wireless networks. This allocation is done to optimize network performance, meet Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, and ensure fair usage among users. The specific allocation methods depend on factors such as network topology, traffic patterns, interference levels, and the

type of wireless technology being used. In PLS, resource allocation is considered as keyless less secrecy or SNR-based secrecy and measured in terms of secrecy rate, secrecy outage probability, equivocation, and channel resolvability.

1) Game Theoretic Approach

Game theory is famous for modeling conflicting mutual consequences and helping decision-making. Primarily, economics has used it to model competing companies in a common marketplace. Later, it has been adopted in biology, politics, computer science, and wireless communications. Game theory is a prominent part of mathematics and is attributed to John von Neumann and Oskar Morgenstern as they published a book titled "Theory of Games and Economic Behaviour" in 1944. This was considered a breakthrough in mathematics and economics, especially when John Nash contributed a model for the equilibrium of the n-person game in 1950.

For the past few years, researchers in wireless communications have been considering game theory for resource allocation in the presence of eavesdroppers. As game theory is based on competition among multiple users with objective conflicts, rational behaviors of wireless users can be characterized [149]. Based on the concept of games, wireless users, strategies, and UAV-enabled communications can be categorized into three parts: wireless users, strategies, and rewards as given in Table 6; however, it depends on the technical application [150].

TABLE 6. Components of games in UAV-enabled wireless communications

Component	Description
Wireless users	AUEs or GUs are considered players in the game competing for contradictory goals
Strategies	It could be UAV placement, task servicing, expropriation of intruders, etc.
Rewards	Rewards could be optimized in resource allocation, coverage improvements, performance enhancement, and secure communication among legitimate users in the presence of eavesdroppers. Rewards and payoffs are used interchangeably in the literature.

Game theory has two types of games: cooperative games and non-cooperative games. The cooperative games are based on the users' agreements prior to the selection of the action, resulting in a change of strategies and collective rewards. In UAV-enabled wireless communications, UAVs agreed upon the temporary alliance to form cooperative games that can be used for task allocation [149]. In [151], differential cooperative games among wireless users are considered to provide network security. In wireless power communication networks, the Stackelberg game is used to solve energy demands with incentives and secure communication among legitimate users [152]. This model

is further explored with a BS, Power Station (PS), IRS, and communicating devices [153]. Some legitimate users affected by Trojan's horse are considered eavesdroppers who can compete for Wireless Information Transfer (WIT) or Wireless Power Transfer (WPT). It is assumed that the PS belongs to a different vendor, the Stackelberg game is used for secure communication and energy trading, and the backward induction method is used to formulate the equilibrium solution [154].

In contrast to cooperative games, non-cooperative games allow the competing users to choose the best strategy selfishly to maximize their rewards with minimum cost. In UAV-enabled wireless communications, game theory can be used in optimal placement of UAV [155] to enhance the coverage area [156], energy optimization [157], performance optimization [149], security [158]. A non-cooperative game theory can be used to formulate the anti-eavesdropping strategy by optimal UAV selection as BS and as jammer [159]. In SWIPT-NOMA, when a UAV is harvesting energy and idle UAVs are helping in the presence of eavesdropper, a utility function can be formulated for both idle and active UAVs using Stackelberg game [160].

Game theory in wireless communications has many advantages over conventional techniques, especially when it comes to resource allocation in consideration of PLS. Apart from the significance, games for resource allocation, trajectory design, and interference management in UAV-enabled communications still need to be addressed.

2) Trajectory Design Approach

The trajectory design of UAVs is a paramount aspect of their operation. It involves the planning and calculation of the path that the UAV will take during a mission, taking into account factors such as flight speed, altitude, and waypoints. The trajectory design process typically starts with defining mission objectives and constraints, such as the maximum and minimum altitudes, flight speed, and the need to avoid restricted airspace or obstacles. Once these factors are defined, the UAV's flight path can be planned using mathematical and trajectory planning algorithms. The final trajectory must be computationally efficient and safe while meeting the mission objectives. *H. Pan et al. have conducted research on optimizing joint power and 3D trajectory for UAV-enabled communications, specifically addressing the challenges posed by environmental obstacles in [161]. Their work focuses on developing algorithms to enhance energy efficiency and connectivity in complex environments where UAVs must navigate obstacles while maintaining optimal power distribution. Another combined optimization problem has been considered for a UAVs-aided D2D network to maximize network capacity, minimize UAV deployment, and reduce energy consumption by optimizing factors, such as UAV number, position, power, velocity, channel allocation, and device pairing [162].*

Imperatively, UAVs are considered in wireless communications to create a LOS link. However, it also leads the UAV to security dreads [163], [164]. The trajectory design, along with resource allocation, is one of the classical techniques used to secure the communication link from an eavesdropper. A 2D trajectory design with bandwidth allocation is proposed for maximization of secrecy rate in UAV-relying networks [165], and similar work is done in [166] for joint power allocation and optimized power allocation through deep RL algorithms. A 3D trajectory design of UAVs for serving GUs in the presence of ground eavesdroppers is studied with a constraint on the QoS of legitimate users [167]. In [168], the authors presented the 3D trajectory for maximization of Worst-Case Secrecy Rate (WCSR) by taking constraints over the avoidance of UAV collision and speed and proposed the variable speed of UAV. Joint resource allocation, such as bandwidth and energy and trajectory design considering the location of eavesdroppers and legitimate users is addressed where the relaying UAV maneuver with higher speed closer to the eavesdropper and reduces the power [165]. Jue Wang *et al.* gave a very clear and comprehensive sketch of trajectory design by classifying into the implicit trajectory and fixed trajectory and their optimization. Comparison of different surveys on trajectory design in UAV communications is also discussed [169].

3) Artificial Noise (AN)

In wireless communication systems, AN adds random interference to a signal to make it more difficult for an eavesdropper or unauthorized user to intercept and decode the signal. It is considered one of the promising techniques to enhance the security and privacy of wireless transmissions. It is important to note that the use of AN in wireless communications is a complex and active field of research, and the specific techniques used for AN generation and application will depend on the specific wireless system and application.

AN was initially proposed by R. Negi and S. Goel [125] considering two scenarios: multiple antennas transmit to a legitimate receiver in the eavesdropper's presence and single antenna broadcasting with multiple relays, which further provides the link to the legitimate user. The same authors extend this work to MIMO systems, and AN is generated to degrade the eavesdropper link in the case where its strength is better than the legitimate link. Similarly, for non-correlated MIMO Rayleigh fading channels, the secrecy rate is analyzed using AN [170] and further generalized for correlated channels by analyzing ergodic secrecy capacity [164]. In an invited paper, authors reveal the securing strategy in the A2G channel, assuming the full-duplex active eavesdropper and malicious jamming concurrently [171]. AN is more effective in amalgamation with trajectory optimization; for example, a UAV periodically sends an information signal to a GU, and it is suspected that information leakage occurs.

Hence, the UAV is supposed to split the power, one carrying information to GU while the other introducing interference to the rest of the users [172]. Another case is that the UAV communicates with GU in the first phase of communication, where the GU sends the interfering signal simultaneously to confuse the eavesdropper, followed by the UAV interfering signal in the next phase. This approach shows a significant increase in average secrecy rate [173]. In an almost similar model, one UAV jammer is assumed, and trajectory and AN optimization for probabilistic outage probability with Imperfect CSI are analyzed [174]. In this paper, authors transform the probabilistic model to deterministic through Marcum Q -function and Markov inequality.

Due to the importance of AN in securing wireless communications, researchers have done extensive work in this field. However, UAV-enabled communications aided by IRS should be addressed for beamforming and bandwidth optimization in securing communication. In IRS-aided wireless networks, serving UAVs with beams during the maneuver and generating interference signals for the rest of the users is a challenging task, especially on the controller side of the IRS.

C. Channel Coding

In wireless communications, channel coding refers to adding redundancy to the data being transmitted to improve reliability and protect the data against errors and channel effects like noise and interference. This redundancy helps to protect the transmitted data against unauthorized access and interference from malicious adversaries [175]. Better channel coding makes it more difficult for an eavesdropper to intercept and understand the information being transmitted. Additionally, certain types of channel coding, such as secure polar coding [176], are designed to provide confidentiality by keeping the information hidden from unauthorized parties. The wiretap channel codes of Wyner's model are analyzed using i.i.d constructed codes and proved that the minimum achievable secrecy component describes the exact exponent for an average code in the same ensemble [177], shows the average leakage in information to an eavesdropper. The secrecy codes, such as Low-Density Parity-Check (LDPC) code, are established and optimized to achieve secrecy and further maximized using the nested sparse graph-based approach [178]. A design for a transceiver using LDPC codes is proposed for full-duplex UAV-assisted communications [179]. The system model comprises a terrestrial BS, a UAV relay, and GUs.

Polar codes were introduced in 2008 by E. Arıkan, and one of the key purposes is to achieve the capacity of a wide range of channels (such as binary-input memoryless channels) with a low complexity encoding and decoding algorithm [180]. In other words, polar codes can approach the theoretical maximum amount of data that can be transmitted over a given channel with a relatively simple coding scheme [181]. Polar codes are based on the concept of channel

polarization, which refers to the phenomenon where some channels become very good (i.e., have a low error rate) while others become very bad (i.e., have a high error rate) as the code length increases. The data bits are then assigned to the good channels, while the bad channels are used for error correction. The polar coding algorithm uses this phenomenon to construct a code that can approach the capacity of a given channel. The encoding and decoding of polar codes are based on the use of a specific transformation called the polar transform, which is used to map the data bits to the channel inputs.

Due to the efficiency of polar codes and capacity achieved close to Shannon, these codes are considered in NTN networks in 5G and beyond. The performance comparison of LDPC and polar codes for the transmission of over 7.8 km is given, showing the polar codes are better in results [182]. The performance of polar codes for uplink channel narrow-band IoTs is analyzed, and results are shown in terms of Block Error Rate (BLER) [183]. A novel design of polar code is presented by Hien and Tra for HAP UAV-enabled communications [184]. In the presented model, HAP UAV is up to 20 km above the ground, serving GUs with assumptions of Rician fading channel and Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN).

D. Secret Key Generation (SKG)

In the PLS of wireless communications, SKG refers to the process of creating a secret key that can be used to encrypt and decrypt the communication between the sender and the receiver. The key is typically generated by using a shared secret between the sender and the receiver, which can be derived from a physical characteristic of the wireless channel. There are several methods for SKG in PLS, such as channel-based key generation, key pre-distribution, random key generation and key generation using Physical Unclonable Function (PUF). In channel-based key generation, the secret key is generated by measuring the physical characteristics of the wireless channel, such as channel randomness, independent channel variation in space, and channel reciprocity. The sender and the receiver use the same channel, so they can use the same key. In pre-distribution, the random keys are generated and distributed among the legitimate users before the communication starts. Similarly, in random key generation, the keys are exchanged at the start of the communication. The PUF method is considered more secure as the secret keys are generated from a unique physical characteristic of the device, such as the manufacturing variations in the device.

Suppose $h(t)$ is the common time-varying stochastic-based channel between Alice and Bob, and Alice wants to start communication with Bob. Prior to communication, the common channel needs to be exploited at both ends for SKG. The downlink channel and uplink channel, i.e., Alice to Bob and from Bob to Alice simultaneously, should be the same, which means that the secret keys need to be generated within the coherence time. Coherence time depends on the

correlation between the channels and can be represented mathematically as:

$$T_c = \sqrt{\frac{9}{16\pi f_D^2}}, \quad (16)$$

where f_D is the maximum Doppler shift. To evaluate and quantify the effects of Doppler shift on the C2 link in UAV communications, a comprehensive analysis through simulations to determine the resulting error rate of the received signal and IQ data visualization has been given in [185]. A concrete theoretical foundation has been proposed for the linking of micro-Doppler signatures and maneuverability of small UAVs based on the Doppler spectrum in [186]. Similarly, the impact of multi-directional mobility of UAV-to-Vehicle channels over the Doppler is analyzed in [187], and for UAV-to-satellite calculated in [188].

Fig. 7 illustrates the five main stages of SKG: parameter design, channel probing, quantization, reconciliation, and privacy amplification. Many researchers also consider including a pre-processing step before the quantization stage. The first two steps involve exploiting the reciprocal nature of the wireless channel, followed by quantization. During quantization, samples derived from channel attributes are converted into digital bits, which may not perfectly match between the two legitimate nodes. To address this mismatch, reconciliation is performed through public discussion. Finally, privacy amplification is applied to enhance the key's resilience against eavesdropping.

FIGURE 7. Secret key generation, a block flow diagram

1) Parameter Designing

The fading nature of the wireless channel model impacts the secure communication rate and is taken as an advantage for the secure key generation to achieve a nonzero secrecy rate. This nature of wireless communication leads us to use certain parameters to design the key generation process, including things like the channel conditions [189], the signal-to-noise ratio [190], and the characteristics of the wireless communication systems [191] being used. By carefully selecting these parameters and designing the key generation process

based on them, it is possible to enhance the system's security and make it more resistant to attacks. One example of a parametric design technique is the use of chaotic signals in the key generation process, which can help to increase the entropy of the generated key and make it more difficult for an attacker to predict [192]. The secret keys can be generated opportunistically using the information-theoretic approach by successfully exploiting the fading properties of wireless channels [130].

Due to the maneuverability of UAVs, the angles in 3D space among Aerial User Equipment (AUE) and GU will always be unique and can be utilized for the SKG among legitimate users. In [193], a cylindrical shape is visualized considering the location of GU and UAV, and angles are calculated for the MIMO A2G channel. This model is further used for SKG.

2) Channel Probing

The channel probing in wireless communications is used to determine the properties of a wireless channel before transmitting data. This information is then used to optimize communication and ensure the security of the transmitted key [194]. Probing the channel can be done in several ways, such as by sending a known pilot signal and measuring its properties at the receiver [195]. This information can be used to estimate the channel's characteristics, such as its gain, phase, and delay, as well as its level of noise, interference, and fading.

In wireless SKG applications, channel probing is used to determine the properties of the wireless channel before the secret key is transmitted. Knowing the channel properties in advance allows the sender and receiver to adapt their communication systems to the channel conditions and improve the performance of the key generation process. Additionally, it can also be used to ensure the security of the key, as it allows the sender and receiver to detect and prevent eavesdropping or jamming attacks. The probing is based on the concept of channel reciprocity and taking advantage of it, as most of the generation of secret keys exploit TTD. Hence, legitimate users transmit the pilots to estimate the CSI, and the time required for this process is constrained by the coherence time, which restricts the pilot overheads. It has been observed that the pilot overhead linearly increased with the number of antennas, so in small-scale MIMO systems, the CSI are highly correlated and secret keys as well [196]. However, the massive-MIMO systems are more complex, and pairwise SKG is more difficult. A novel SKG scheme for a multi-user massive MIMO system is proposed based on Channel Dimensionality Reduction (CDR) [197]. Many attributes can be taken into consideration while channel probing. Important attributes include:

Level-Crossing Rate (LCR)

The first order fading statistics, such as PDF and CDF, do not provide any information regarding the distribution

of signals over time. Second-order fading statistics such as LCR, Average Fade Duration (AFD), and Average Contiguous Duration (ACD) describe the fading behavior of a given signal over time. These metrics can potentially help in generating secret keys with good randomness properties. LCR is defined as the average number of times the given signal crosses a certain amplitude threshold value. For instance, both legitimate users can measure the average number of times the signal crosses a given threshold within a specific observation period. The LCR can also help in the selection of suitable samples for SKG. Mathur et al. have proposed a level-crossing algorithm for SKG based on the LCR Rayleigh fading channels with application for terminals employing 802.11 and 801.11a standards in [198].

Average Fade Duration (AFD)

AFD is the ratio between the total time for which the received signal stays below a threshold value and the total number of experienced fades. AFD can also be used for the SKG on communication ends.

Average Contiguous Duration (ACD)

LCR and AFD characterize the fading rate of a signal with reference to a single amplitude threshold. The recently proposed ACD metric in [199] characterizes the fading rate of a signal with reference to multiple amplitude thresholds, making it a more suitable choice for applications such as quantization, compression, coding, etc. Its application for SKG has been discussed in [200].

Envelope

Secret keys can be generated using the power level of the received signals.

Delay Profile

The auto-correlation function of the impulse response calculated at $\Delta t = 0$ is called delay profile (DP). DP defines how the power is distributed between the different delayed echoes. DP can be used for SKG.

Angle of Arrival (AoA) The legitimate user can use angular-domain measurements for the SKG. To acquire these measurements, multi-antenna systems, such as antenna arrays, MIMO, and massive MIMO are necessary at the terminals. The AoA statistics are a function of the spatial position of the transmitter, scattering elements, and the receiver. Consequently, an eavesdropper positioned differently is unable to observe the same channel.

3) Quantization

Quantization is a major step in the SKG used to generate the bits to obtain the preliminary key after estimating the received signal. Quantization could be applied to the smaller block and the large block depending on the fluctuation of the RSS. Quantization is a process in which a continuous signal is converted into a digital signal by mapping it to a finite number of discrete levels. The purpose of quantization in SKG in wireless communications is to convert continuous analog signals into digital signals that users can process

and map to a finite number of discrete levels, further used to generate random numbers. Different attributes, such as thermal or electrical noise [201], can be used as the basis for secret keys in encryption algorithms. By converting these signals into digital format, it becomes possible to extract random numbers that can be used to generate secure keys for encrypted communications. Quantization is a critical component of many key generation schemes in wireless communications, as it provides randomness and unpredictability due to the random nature of the wireless channels required for secure key generation.

In most cases, the magnitude response function is considered, which is part of the RSS and is further used for quantization. For quantization, the sampling is done through the Algorithm given in [202], which only takes the sample above the threshold value in the Level Crossing Rate. Similarly, a quantization algorithm is proposed in [203] for generalized gamma distributed channels, and extended to a new concept of ACD is proposed in [199], giving better results. The randomness of the generated secret keys was tested using the NIST suite. This method has not yet been tested over UAV communications. However, an adaptive quantization algorithm is discussed for vehicular communications with the same approach [204]. A robust encryption system based on updating index parameters to ensure secure key generation has been proposed in [205], where a mutual connection between index parameter keys is created within the transmitter and receiver configuration. Each individual index parameter generates a unique key that varies over time. These parameters are then transformed into a binary bit stream and attached to the end of the frame header.

In a TDD system SKG is way easier as compared to FDD due to the frequency difference used for uplink and downlink. In such systems, the phase differences and AoA are the better options to consider instead of other RSSI parameters. A curve fitting non-uniform quantization algorithm and Slepian-Wolf coding for reconciliation is used after exploiting the phase difference between the neighbor antennas for FDD system [206]. Quantization is considered the most important part in SKG, in addition, a pre-processing like encryption prior to quantization can also increase the security strength of the secret key [207]. The authors in [208] proposed a Continuous Encryption Function (CEF) to produce the sequence of quasi-continuous pseudo-random numbers.

4) Reconciliation

Reconciliation is a process in SKG in wireless communications that is used to correct errors that occur during the transmission of secret keys. It is a critical step in generating secure keys for encrypted communications. It helps ensure that both parties have the same secret key, even if errors are made during transmission. The reconciliation process

works by comparing the key generated by one party with the key generated by the other party and making necessary corrections to ensure that both keys are identical. This process can involve several techniques, including error detection and correction codes [209], data compression [210], or secure two-way communication to compare and reconcile the keys. The goal of reconciliation is to ensure that the final secret key is secure and usable for encryption, even in the presence of noise, interference, or other errors during transmission. The probability of error always increases with the improper estimation, which leads the receiver to improper quantization. This kind of quantization error results in key entropy loss and can only be possibly accommodated with the help of reconciliation [211]. Without reconciliation, these errors could cause the keys generated by the two parties to be different, leading to communication failure or security breaches. In [209], the authors used polar codes to reconcile the secret keys, and the results show betterment in KGR with reduced KMP.

Presently, reconciliation in QKD is the main focus among the researchers, as the lattice-based approach in post-quantum cryptography guarantees strong theoretical security, which is considered hard to break with quantum computers [212].

Mobility is one of the major reasons in drones and vehicles to introduce channel dynamics resulting in KMP, as most of the research in this case is carried out for short-range communications, such as Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), ZigBee, and mm-wave. In 6G, the main objective is to accommodate the high-speed vehicles into the wireless standards, so long-range communications for SKG could be a better solution to address the 6G security challenges [213]. Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) is one of the 6G candidates that deals with high-speed vehicles and can also be considered for SKG in UAV-enabled wireless communications. The OTFS approach can outperform the existing technologies in securing communication among moving legitimate users because of the dependency of channels on their relative velocities [214].

5) Privacy strengthening

Privacy amplification in the PLS-based SKG refers to increasing the privacy of a shared secret key between two communication parties. It involves transforming a weak, potentially vulnerable key into a stronger, more secure one using mathematical algorithms. Privacy amplification aims to ensure that even if an eavesdropper has some partial information about the key, it will still be unable to determine the entire key. This process is crucial for the security of many cryptographic systems and helps to prevent attacks such as eavesdropping and hacking.

In classical cryptography schemes, the public keys are used by legitimate users, and symmetric keys are used to cipher at the transmitter side and decipher at the receiver end.

In Fig. 8 (a), PLS-based secret keys are generated on both legitimate users using the common statistical channel. In case Fig. 8 (b), QKD is used to generate the secret keys and distribute them among legitimate users. The same key can be utilized for encryption and decryption on both sides. The QKD transceivers encapsulate a set of hardware and software components used for QKD within a defined secure boundary. The QKD relies on both classical channels and quantum channels. The quantum channel is used to transmit quantum signals in which quantum states, such as the polarization of a single photon, convey information.

FIGURE 8. (a): Physical layer security-based secret key generation, and (b): Quantum key distribution

E. Trade-offs in Network Performance Metrics

In beyond 5G communication systems, achieving an optimal balance between security and performance is critical. Although PLS offers the potential for secure communication without relying on computationally expensive cryptographic methods, its implementation may have impacts on other key network performance metrics such as throughput and latency. In UAV-enabled communications or in NTN, PLS also has direct effects on energy efficiency. Understanding these trade-offs is significantly important for the design of efficient and secure networks.

1) PLS and Throughput

PLS techniques such as beamforming [215]–[217] or artificial noise generation [218]–[220] require additional power and bandwidth, which can reduce the effective data rate. For UAVs, mobility and frequent changes in topology make it difficult to maintain stable channels, further complicating the balance between secrecy rate and throughput. In NTNs, where long propagation delays and varying channel conditions are common, the trade-off becomes even more prominent. Techniques such as adaptive modulation and

coding schemes can mitigate throughput loss while ensuring security in these dynamic settings [221].

2) PLS and Latency

URLLC is an important factor in 6G and beyond communications, especially in UAV and NTN applications, where real-time services such as remote piloting or disaster response are required. Improving PLS may introduce additional signaling overhead and processing time, which can conflict with the low-latency requirements of these systems [222]. For instance, SKG processes, such as channel probing and reconciliation [223], can delay communication, especially in NTNs where propagation delays are inherently high [224]. In UAV networks, rapid changes in topology demand frequent re-establishment of secure links, further heightening latency issues. Employing lightweight PLS schemes and leveraging edge computing in NTN gateways or UAV control units can help reduce latency impacts [225]–[227].

3) PLS and EE

EE is an important aspect of wireless communications, especially for UAVs with limited onboard power and NTNs, where satellites and ground stations often operate under power constraints. PLS techniques, such as cooperative jamming [78] or secure beamforming [215], can consume significant energy, impacting the overall efficiency of these systems. For UAVs, this trade-off can limit operational time and coverage, while in NTNs, it can strain resource allocation and reduce the capacity for other essential functions [25]. Employing energy-aware PLS algorithms and optimizing power allocation can help mitigate these effects [44].

F. Lesson Learned

In NTNs such as satellite or UAV-based communication, both SKG and resource allocation techniques can play essential roles in ensuring security, but from different angles. Deciding which one is better depends on the specific use case, requirements, and network challenges, and a comparison is given in Table 5. However, SKG is advantageous in environments where lightweight, dynamic, and PLS are needed. It is a promising approach for NTN communications, especially in UAV-to-ground or satellite-to-ground links where channel randomness can be exploited. However, its effectiveness depends on the channel reciprocity and key rate requirements.

In NTNs, where mobility and large distances create varying propagation environments, SKG can exploit the inherent randomness and reciprocity of the wireless channel to generate cryptographic keys without the need for heavy computational resources or complex infrastructure. This lightweight security mechanism is ideal for NTNs, which often involve power-constrained devices like UAVs and require real-time communication. Additionally, SKG provides dynamic key generation, meaning that keys can be refreshed with each

communication session, offering enhanced security compared to static key management systems. By using real-time channel measurements, SKG ensures that even if an adversary intercepts part of the communication, it is nearly impossible for them to reconstruct the key unless they can exactly replicate the legitimate channel. Thus, SKG's ability to adapt to the high mobility, dynamic environments, and resource constraints of NTNs makes it a highly efficient and effective security solution for these networks.

While SKG offers significant advantages over keyless methods and traditional cryptographic techniques in securing NTNs, it faces several challenges. For instance, the characterization of Eve's channel, bounds are not categorized for finite blocks, and translating theoretical advancements into practical applications remains in its early stages. SKG exploits the randomness of channel measurements; however, in scenarios involving flat channels, the KGR will drop to zero, the KAP will reach one, and SKG will become unnecessary. Therefore, achieving a balanced trade-off is crucial to harmonize KGR, key success rate, and correlation factors. Additionally, determining the appropriate key length requires a careful balance during SKG, considering the sensitivity of wireless transmission and the computational capacity of the end devices, to ensure that latency requirements are not compromised.

IV. UAVs in Communication Technologies

UAVs have become integral to the advancement of modern communication technologies, offering flexibility, mobility, and extended coverage capabilities. Their integration with advanced systems such as NOMA, RIS, MIMO, OTFS, and PLS underscores their transformative potential in enhancing wireless networks. UAVs can significantly improve spectral efficiency, support secure communications, and manage resources more effectively, particularly in challenging or remote environments. In NTNs, UAVs are well-positioned to address critical issues such as signal obstructions and URLLC and enhance overall network resilience.

We have summarized this convergence of technologies, focusing on their application in UAV-assisted communications, while also outlining future directions and open issues. These include optimizing UAV energy consumption, strengthening PLS to safeguard against eavesdropping, and addressing regulatory, operational, and technical challenges. Solving these issues will be crucial to unlocking the full potential of UAV-based communication systems in the future wireless landscape.

A. UAV in NOMA

NOMA is a promising technique to accommodate a high number of GU and AUE due to its ability to employ the superimposition of signals. NOMA was previously used in satellite communications, later it has been considered in recent cellular communications releases/standards. In [228], Z. Ding *et al.* discussed two cases of transmission phase

with receiver perspective, outage performance, and ergodic sum rate of randomly deployed GUs. In the start, NOMA was considered with user pairing [229] for sum-rate maximization [230]. Recently, researchers started considering NOMA in UAV-enabled wireless communications. In congested outdoor locations, such as traffic jams, stadiums, concerts, or disaster areas, where wireless communication networks are needed for specific time intervals, NOMA-based UAV networks can be deployed to maximize the minimum achievable rates [231]. In their proposed work, they divided the coverable region of UAV into two fields, i.e., the nearby field and the far field. The available bandwidth is uniformly divided among the GU in the nearby field, and then the optimal GU from the far field is superimposed with one of the nearby users.

However, the superposition nature addressed the connectivity problem, which also leads to privacy dreads. Considering this privacy apprehension, the secrecy of all the superimposed users is handled cumulatively, and secrecy sum-rate maximization is proposed [232], but the individual secrecy still remains equivocal. Recently, the cooperative nature of NOMA has been exploited in which the stronger user is helping, the weaker user with a maximum secrecy rate without compromising on the QoS of each individual user [233]. Researchers also considered the PLS enhancement through dynamic power allocation based on the geographic location of the UAV, UT, and eavesdropper. The same scenario for the A2G channel with stochastic-based LOS and NLOS models is taken into consideration for closed-form expression of secrecy outage probability [234]. They used dynamic power allocation to legitimate users, further categorized into two based on reliability and security requirements. Another UAV is used to introduce AN to illegitimate users, fulfilling the security needs of the legitimate user. As users are superimposed in NOMA on the basis of their channel conditions, hence, more power is allocated to the user with weaker channel conditions, which leads the user to security risk. This problem can be sewn up by introducing the jamming signals generated by the GUs. However, a trade-off can be made on power consumption optimization. This trade-off, along with the trajectory of UAV, is taken into consideration for optimization analyzing the instantaneous achievable rate on the UTs [235].

To overcome the energy depletion at UTs, SWIPT is used in amalgamation with NOMA and mmwave in UAV-enabled wireless communications [236]. In the mmwave-NOMA networks, when a UAV is serving K number of GUs with a specific region called a protected zone, it is considered as free of eavesdroppers. In this scenario, beamforming and trajectory design for UAVs to maximize the sum secrecy rate of the system is only possible in the case of ascertainable eavesdroppers. The same model is studied with localization of detrimental eavesdropper, and it is concluded that channel exploitation from LAPs could be more vulnerable as compared to HAPs because of having small pathloss distance and

larger relative angles [237]. This work is further extended by introducing SWIPT and shaping the protected zone by analyzing the sum secrecy rate for worst-case and best-case scenarios on the basis of decoding capabilities [238].

Another interesting case is in which a UAV can be utilized as an untrusted relay between the source and destination. Suppose the untrusted relay UAV receives a SWIPT signal from BS and extracts the power signal in the first phase to increase the flight time. In the second phase, the UAV transmits the information signal to a number of users using the NOMA scheme. To enhance the PLS in such cases, a jammer is considered, which transmits noise and powerful signal to the UAV, which helps the UAV to harvest the power signal and, in parallel, make the information signal secure from the UAV [239].

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

NOMA is a promising technique that can better utilize the available spectrum and accommodate a maximum number of users in this hyper-connected society. However, the superposition principle leads the user to security risks. In UAV-enabled wireless communications, the PLS still needs to be addressed and should be taken into consideration in Visible Light communications (VLC) precoding and integrated Terrestrial-UAV-Satellite networks (ITUSN). Some of the Open issues in UAV-NOMA wireless communication networks are as follows:

- In NOMA-enabled UAV wireless communications, spectrum sensing to cater to the interference issues needs more concentration from the researchers. Presently, the conventional spectrum sensing techniques are used in NOMA, a novel algorithm specifically for the NOMA-UAV networks, and the stochastic-based closed-form solution for detection and correlation among multiple users are open issues to be addressed.
- As UAVs have the advantage of manoeuvrability over the terrestrial networks, hence, the channel gains change with the motion of UAVs resulting in user pairing. It is recommended to have a phenomenon that allows UAVs to choose intelligently the users for pairing.

B. UAV in RSMA

In principle, Rate-Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) is based on rate splitting, which splits the user message into private and common parts. RSMA provides a more secure physical layer paradigm for non-orthogonal transmission. RSMA is the combination of NOMA and Space Division Multiple Access (SDMA) and has the ability to switch to any of them (by reducing the power of the common part of the message signal) or switch in between them (by interference management) [240]. The significance and promising secure transmission of RSMA motivate the researchers to consider it in UAV communications to extend the coverage, however,

no sufficient work has been done yet. Authors in [241] considered the downlink scenario for RSMA precoding and UAV placement, in which UAV serves multiple GUs. A novel algorithm is proposed to solve the non-convex optimization problem and maximization of the weighted sum rate. In multi-UAV networks, the interference introduced by UAVs to each other causes system performance. A mathematical model for stochastic-based geometry is proposed to overcome the randomness in topologies and interference in the networks [242]. Similarly, throughput and outage probability optimization is carried out in [243] for Nakagami- m small-scale fading. Lin *et al.* presented an interference suppression strategy using RSMA in Satellite and Aerial Integrated Networks (SAIN) for GUs and IoT devices [244]. H. Bastami *et al.* considered a model in which two legitimate users are communicating in the presence of an eavesdropper having multiple antennas. A WCSR is studied in two phases of a cooperative rate splitting scheme in downlink UAV communications [245]. The first phase is secured by designing rate splitting precoder from the eavesdropper, while the second is secured by introducing AN in the direction of the eavesdropper using a Maximum Ratio Transmission (MRT) beamformer resulting in the maximization of the system secrecy rate.

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

Presently, researchers are considering RSMA with emerging technologies in next-generation wireless communication networks, such as IRS [246], VLC [247], mmwave [248], and THz [249]. However, most of the work on RSMA is considered resource allocation, performance analysis and optimization. It is observed that very little work has been done so far in combination with the 6G enabling technologies, especially from the PLS perspective. A few of the open issues are as follows:

- The quantization contortions are more admissible in RSMA but in amalgamation with mmwave, it would be more remunerative to exploit the sparse behaviour of the mmwave channel and reduce the feedback overhead by squashing the pilots into low-dimensional matrices.
- Sometimes, high variations in terrestrial networks lead to deep fades, so SAIN is recommended to provide ubiquitous connectivity to GUs, AUE, and IoT devices illustrated in Fig. 3. The performance of RSMA in terms of connectivity and reliability is expected to be promising in integrated networks.
- In UAV communications, the 3D motion leads to 3D channel anatomy affecting the channel tracking, which eventually causes co-channel interference. It was observed that this interference can be mitigated through trajectory designing with RSMA, which still needs the scientific community's attention.
- The PLS has already been considered in [245], [250], [251], and [252] but still is not considered in the SAIN.

C. UAV in OTFS

Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) is a 2D modulation scheme used to transform the time-varying channel to a time-invariant channel in the Delay-Doppler (DD) domain. The existing technologies considered for 5G have failed to provide reliable communication to high-speed vehicles, such as planes, bullet trains, and high-speed UAVs. Therefore, OTFS is considered one of the promising candidates for the 6G wireless. The time-variant channels, i.e., Wide-Sense stationary (WSS) channels and Uncorrelated Scattering (US) channels, are examined and successfully transformed to time-invariant channels [253] through time-frequency duality. Bello presented a kernel system function that omits the Doppler-Delay spread, and Delay-Doppler spread functions in Linear time-variant channels [254]. Inspired by Bello's work, the OTFS modulation technique is introduced by Hadani *et al.* in [255]. The authors claim it can hold the performance up to 500 km/h and give a comparative review with Bit Error Rate (BER) graphs against SNR-dB, showing OTFS is better than the OFDMA standard, which is considered for 5G. The Doppler and modulation possibilities have been studied for uplink NOMA in [256].

In disaster areas where high-speed UAVs are going to be deployed, UAVs can be deployed initially to inspect the area and locate the victims where UAVs need to be deployed to enable wireless communications. In such a scenario where the emergency teams, rehabilitation teams, and inspection teams, along with the affected users, need wireless connectivity, OTFS can serve better by maintaining 6G standards [257]. In SAIN, OTFS could outperform the existing schemes when a Low Earth Orbital (LEO) satellite moves at high speed, serving the GUs through UAV cooperation. It is assumed that the UAV-to-GU channel follows the Nakagami- m distribution and Satellite-to-UAV/GU follows the shadowing Rice distribution, studied for a closed form solution of the outage probability, the positive gain with UAV cooperation, and the significance over 5G technologies are analyzed [258]. In [259], three aircraft are considered with the relative speed of 4320 Km/h, communicating with each other in mesh topology using 13-18 GHz of carrier frequency and from 1 up to 5 MHz of bandwidth. A performance analysis is given in terms of BER against SNR considering the two-ray propagation model and assumption of complex Gaussian distribution.

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

OTFS is considered for 6G technologies due to the promising outputs in high-speed DD environments. According to the current 5G NR standard for V2X, i.e., IEEE 802.11bd, a dominant part of waveforms is based on OFDM where mitigating the impact of channel variations is carried out through subcarrier spacing or by insertion of midamble with trading off on spectrum efficiency. OTFS has the capability to handle these variations in the channel in the DD domain;

hence, OTFS can be explored for V2X communications in 6G networks. In mmwave with high frequencies, it results in inter-carrier interference (ICI) even for low to medium velocities, which is again overcome with subcarrier spacing. Similarly, in LAP and LEO satellites, taking care of the channel fluctuations imposed by the Doppler shift/spread Doppler pushes us in the saddle of low data rate to provide ubiquitous connectivity. In both of these cases, OTFS can perform better due to channel sparsity in the spatial domain. A few of the challenges are listed below:

- The channel is always sparse in the Time-Frequency domain but it may not be the same in the DD domain because of spreading over all the Doppler indices, resulting in more guard spaces in pilot symbols and, eventually, an increment in the communications overhead. It is one of the challenges to propose strategies to overcome this increment in the overhead without compromising on the channel estimation.
- Due to high mobility and multipath effects, ISI could affect data detection. Hence, efficient quantities need to be introduced with complexity trade-offs for better detection of symbols.
- In UAV communications, beamforming or precoding using OTFS is a challenging task to exploit the angle of freedom in the spatial domain. Particularly, if we discuss the MIMO case, TDD is the limitation, how could it be explored in DD domains? More sophisticated models need to be designed as a countermeasure to such limitations.

D. UAVs with Massive MIMO

Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (MIMO) is used to enhance QoS, throughput, and capacity of the wireless link and can be achieved by the installation of multiple antennas at both source and destination. MIMO makes the system efficient by transmitting multiple independent streams from multiple antennas at the same time and frequency. This efficiency is further enhanced in Multi-User MIMO (MU-MIMO), where different users receive different streams from the same transmitter at the same time and frequency. In the growing world of wireless devices, radio resources need to be utilized where a maximum number of users are served and their demands fulfilled with ubiquitous connectivity. Hence, researchers proposed the massive-MIMO (mMIMO) concept, where the number of antennas at the transmitter is considered at least double the number of antennae at the receiver. The main three enabling concepts of mMIMO are spatial multiplexing, spatial diversity, and beamforming/precoding [260]. While discussing the mMIMO in one of the Bell Lab documents [261], T. L. Marzetta claimed that mMIMO could accomplish the Shannon capacity limit stated in [118], in three ways, given below:

- Acquiring of CSI in TDD is independent of the number of antennas at the transmitter,

- Number of antennas at the transmitter should be at least double the number of antennae at the receiver,
- Linear precoding coupled with linear decoding on downlink and uplink, respectively, employs on the BS.

Motivated by the importance of the mMIMO, a cell-free environment is proposed to serve the AUEs in parallel with GUs with the same frequency bands without compromising on the QoS of the GU [262]. In combination with mmwave, UAV space-time frequency time-variant channel models are exploited and used for the 3D run time motion trajectory, self-rotation, and velocities of UAVs in single and twin clusters [263]. Similarly, mMIMO is used in the uplink from the ground station towards the swarm of UAVs for 3D deployment, further optimized with the help of Nash equilibrium game theory [264]. An authentication-based precoder design based on AN and data transmission at the same time is proposed for uplink mMIMO UAV communications [265]. Their results contain the ergodic secrecy rate and secret key recovery probability.

During the literature review, it was observed that most of the work in mMIMO UAV communications is done on the uplink from Ground BS (GBS) to AUE. However, the authors in [266] consider UAV-assisted wireless with mmwave in mMIMO. They assumed a single UAV with multiple antennas, multiple GBS with a large number of antennas mounted on them, and multiple numbers of GUs served by GBS and UAV through hybrid beamforming. The performance analysis is carried out in terms of sum rate against SNR and UAV altitude. Furthermore, the UAV association with the concerned GBS is also analyzed.

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

It can be summarized that while a categorization has been acknowledged in the literature between the UAV as a part of the service provider and the UAV as an AUE, most of the published research considers the UAV as an AUE. However, UAVs can also outperform if used as aerial relays or ABS, particularly, the network of UAVs in the air with joint beamforming with terrestrial networks. Other usage scenarios of UAVs are to perform precoding and decoding on the terrestrial BS while UAVs are used as transponders. In the same case, UAVs can add some AN to the received signal to make the link more secure. Some open issues in mMIMO that can benefit from the use of secure UAVs can be summarized as follows:

- The efficient way of tracking the beam in moving UAVs or GUs, like vehicles, needs to be addressed.
- The concept of using secure UAVs for passive holographic MIMO surfaces and reconfigurable intelligent surfaces involves leveraging the capabilities of UAVs to enhance the security and performance of communication systems. The holographic surfaces can introduce secure beamforming and signal shaping, minimizing

the risk of eavesdropping or unauthorized access to the communication channels. RIS elements on UAVs can contribute to controlled signal directionality, minimizing the risk of unintentional signal leakage and enhancing communication privacy. Additionally, secure communication protocols can be integrated to protect against unauthorized access and cyber threats.

- Exploiting the sparsity of the signal addresses the compressed sensing optimization problem along with pilot decontamination and channel estimation.
- UAVs can selectively activate and deactivate specific antennas based on user demand or network conditions. This selective activation contributes to energy-efficient deployments, conserving power resources when full antenna deployment is not necessary.

FIGURE 9. RIS: working principle

E. UAV in RIS communications

Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces, also known as Intelligent Reflective Surfaces, are multiple passive reflecting surfaces having length L_x and width L_y greater than the λ of the receiving signal, governed by the programmable controller. Fig. 9 illustrates the basic working principle of a RIS, showing the geometry of incident and reflected electromagnetic waves. RIS consists of a surface with adjustable elements that can manipulate the phase and direction of the incoming signals. This enables the surface to enhance signal propagation and optimize wireless communication performance by reflecting waves toward desired locations. This concept of reflections was first introduced by L. Subrt and P. Pechac, proposing the idea of intelligent reflective walls for smart indoor environments [267]. RIS is considered for 6G wireless communications because of its capability of suppressing interference, coverage, beamforming, and PLS. The physics behind the reflections from passive surfaces and propagation, along with bandwidth calculations, are derived in [268]. To provide ubiquitous connectivity to GUs and AUEs, RIS can be used in different ways, such as RIS mounted on UAV [269], [270], RIS installed on a large building with UAV as BS [271], [272], RIS installed indoor [273] and terrestrial assisted by RIS and UAVs [274]. A recent comparative analysis on RIS deployment in indoor smart environments, as presented in [275], concluded that indoor RIS installations could outperform outdoor setups. Fig. 10 highlights four use cases: (a) RIS mounted on UAVs to provide connectivity to GUs, (b) RIS integrated into large buildings to reflect incident waves toward users, and (c) and (d) RIS-assisted UAV scenarios where indoor users or smart devices receive signals.

Researchers are trying to make communication more secure by considering an RIS with UAV BS, where GUs receive signals directly from ABS and RIS, respectively. It is assumed that a passive eavesdropper can listen to the signals of legitimate users. Keeping constraints on the legitimate user speed with respect to the initial location, direction, and transmit power from the ABS, the secrecy

rate of the legitimate user is optimized with the help of UAV trajectory and phase shifter of RIS [276]. To ensure the LOS communications using mmwave bands in the A2G channel, RISs are deployed in different locations, but due to lack of power on UAV, sophisticated preventive mechanisms can not be applied. Hence, PLS is a better solution to provide information privacy with the help of AN-aided adaptive beamforming. Authors in [277] proposed a novel algorithm for non-convex optimization problems for ABS beamforming, RIS optimal location, and passive beamforming in combination with UAV trajectory. The results are compared with existing algorithms for secrecy rate and proved that the proposed algorithm outperforms the existing ones. The extension of this work is given with an explanation in which the objective problem is divided into sub-problems, i.e., power transmission designing for defined trajectory and beamforming, designing of beamforming for defined trajectory and transmission power, and trajectory designing for given beamforming and transmission power [278]. With CSI assumptions, the secrecy rate in uplink and downlink have been optimized in all three sub-problems, a combined algorithm is proposed, and required results are discussed in terms of average-worst case secrecy rate. Recently, a deep reinforcement learning-based UAV trajectory with passive and active beamforming design has been proposed exploiting the mmwave bands to enhance the overall security of the system [279].

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

RIS provides a low-cost and efficient solution to enable URLLC to have the capability of coverage enhancement with the use of UAVs. However, researchers are facing practical issues with RIS-aided/ assisted UAV communications. Finding the optimal location for the RIS installation in order to ensure the virtual LOS communication between the transmitter and receiver is a challenging optimization problem. From a programming perspective, the efficient

FIGURE 10. UAV communications aided by RIS

matrix configuration needs to be addressed for phase shifters, according to CSI. Some open issues are as follows:

- **RIS phase shift:** RIS does not have the capability to take countermeasures against the CSI. It should be taken into consideration on the controller portion of RIS mounted on UAV.
- **Channel State Acquisition:** First, the UAV is moving in 3D due to which maintaining the LOS between the RIS surfaces and UAV antenna, considering the jittering effect of the UAV, CSI acquisition becomes hard, which is further harder by shadowing effects and scattering phenomenon. A robust model is compulsory to address the external environmental factors.
- **Security:** As UAVs are detectable, it makes them vulnerable to security threats. Hence, safe and secure transmission strategies need to be made to ensure secure transmission between legitimate users through PLS.
- **Beamforming:** RIS does not have the ability for precoding, so, hybrid precoding can be a good solution if controlled by the electrical tilt to increase or decrease the coverage in a specific direction.

F. Machine Learning in UAV-enabled communications

Machine Learning (ML) is a field of data analytics that offers computers the capability to learn and make decisions without explicit programming or human intervention. ML is further classified into three: Supervised Learning (SL), Un-supervised Learning (USL), and Reinforcement Learning (RL). The SL is an ML approach used to train the algorithm with labeled data, while in contrast, the USL is used where labeled data are not required for the training of the algorithm. Another approach called semi-supervised learning (SSL) needs a small amount of data for training and takes a decision on the combination of labeled and unlabeled data. In RL, the algorithm functions on the basis of the feedback provided by the environment and calculates the error. If an error is more than the threshold, the algorithm is considered punished and rewarded for lesser errors, so the algorithm always pursues a better reward. *Table 7 provides a comprehensive summary of various ML models, categorizing each ML approach based*

on its strengths and potential limitations. This structured comparison offers valuable insights for selecting suitable ML techniques adapted or modified to specific applications or constraints within communication systems.

ML in wireless communications has found a strong place in research, particularly in channel modeling [280], resource management [281], [282], beamforming [283], networking [284], trajectory management [285] and localization [286]. In PLS, an ML-based approach is used to secure the cellular-connected UAV [287] where UAVs are being considered in three scenarios, i.e., UAVs in delivery systems, UAVs in real-time multimedia streaming and UAVs in intelligent transportation systems. In this article, the authors have used the Convolution Neural Network (CNN) to train UAVs to classify high-risk geographic locations. A Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is used to avoid the undesirable motion of UAVs caused by the anomaly. Normally, authentication in a large-scale network takes more time than the desired one. Considering this issue, the authors in [288] proposed a Long-Short Term Memory (LSTM) based deep RL technique for authentication in the case of real-time multimedia streaming.

ML in PLS-SKG can also outperform the secret key generated from the random channel samples with improved accuracy. However, the stages discussed in Section D would be modified in ML-based PLS-SKG to advanced channel estimation, quantization, reconciliation, anomaly detection, and privacy amplification. The ML algorithms can be used to estimate the channel through learning from the dynamic environmental characteristics and improve the prediction of channel states. The rest of the stages are already been discussed, however in the anomaly detection stage, ML detect anomalous patterns in the channel measurements that may indicate the presence of an eavesdropper, enhancing the security of the key generation process. The significance of ML in PLS-SKG over PLS-SKG is improved accuracy, adaptability, anomaly detection, and efficiency with the trade-off of computational overhead and algorithm complexity.

1) Future Directions and Open Issues

Considering the role of UAVs in NTN wireless communications and the potential benefits of ML, ensuring PLS becomes crucial. The physical layer is the first line of defense against potential security threats, and integrating advanced ML techniques can significantly enhance its robustness, adaptability, and effectiveness in ensuring secure and reliable communications in a wide range of scenarios. The main challenge in implementing ML algorithms for PLS requires significant computational resources affecting latency, which may somehow affect the UAV's constraints. Data privacy is another very important aspect in collecting and analyzing large amounts of data for ML algorithms, and it must be addressed in a way that respects user privacy and complies

TABLE 7. Classification of ML Models

Category	Supervised Learning	Unsupervised Learning	Semi-supervised Learning	Reinforcement Learning
Learning Agent	Labelled Dataset	Un-labelled Dataset	Combination of labeled and unlabelled Dataset	Self-driven, learn on the basis of feedback
Algorithm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Linear Regression • Support Vector Machine (SVM) • Decision Tree • Logistic Regression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hierarchical clustering • K-mean clustering • Principal component analysis • autoencoders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-trained Bayes classifiers • Co-training • Pseudo labelling • Generative Adversarial Networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Q–Learning • Model Based Value estimation
Benefits	Able to make judgments on the basis of decisions like humans	In case of a new object which is not recognized, can be added to a new category	Requires small labeled dataset in the beginning	Take a decision on the basis of reward and punishment, always seeking for maximum reward
Limitations	New object is not perfectly classified and Large data set is required for training	Large computational power and time-consuming	Complex repetitive process	RL can lead to overburden with excessive states and can vanish the outcomes

with relevant regulations. Some more are summarized in the following points:

- **Beamforming:** ML in UAVs can be used to implement secure beamforming techniques and optimize the pattern in real-time based on environmental changes and user movement, ensuring security and communication efficiency through focusing the signal towards legitimate users while minimizing the leakage to a potential eavesdropper.
- **CSI:** ML can be used to analyze and continuously monitor CSI dynamically and for adaptive encryption schemes, ensuring that only legitimate receivers can decode the information with the correct CSI. ML algorithms have the capability to detect jamming attacks and adjust transmission parameters to minimize the impact while considering algorithm complexities for optimal utilization of computational resources.
- **Authentication:** The unique physical layer characteristics, such as signal fingerprints or channel responses, can be exploited with the help of ML algorithms to make the authentication process harder for adversaries to spoof legitimate users.
- **Localization and Navigation:** ML can be used to empower anti-spoofing measures guaranteeing UAV navigation. Furthermore, a resilient positioning by the integration of sensors’ data and ML algorithms, even in challenging environments, could be one of the important applications of ML.

V. UAV Performance Evaluation

Due to the increasing demands of UAVs in various fields, such as surveillance, delivery, and search and rescue operations, it is inevitable to equip UAVs with reliable wireless capabilities. The performance of these capabilities can be

evaluated in terms of wireless communications with the help of several metrics, including signal strength, packet loss rate, latency, throughput, and EE. The evaluation of these metrics provides insights into the performance of the UAV’s communications system and makes us able to improve or upgrade to better meet the needs of the specific application. However, performance can also be evaluated with respect to the applications, which are discussed below:

A. Payload Communication

The term payload refers to the objects installed over UAVs varying from lightweight, such as cell phones, tablets [80] etc., to heavy loads. The size and weight of the payload can affect the flight time of the UAV due to SWaP limitations [289]. Another concept of the payload is the communication payload, which certainly does not affect flight time but rather demands latency, bandwidth, and reliability. The communication payload or payload communication in UAV communications refers to the transmission of data and information between the payloads [290], which is the onboard equipment of the UAV for its specific mission. The data is gathered from sensors, such as cameras, temperature sensors, infrared sensors, Global Positioning System (GPS), etc., and the data is transferred to the ground station. The critical tasks in a successful mission operation of payload communication are the collection of data and secure transfer to the ground station. The mission also depends on the range or the coverage area of the UAV, HAP covers a larger area than the LAP. In the following subsections, a few cases of payload communication are discussed from a PLS perspective.

1) Live Video Broadcast

The UAV onboard camera captures the video and transmits it to the ground station or other remote location. This capability enables remote monitoring and control, as well as live video streaming feeds for various purposes, such as surveillance, search and rescue operations, or aerial photography. The UAV captures live scenarios and transmits them to a cloud server, where the users can experience the live environment with the help of Virtual Reality (VR) glasses. The same case can be implemented where UAV allows multiple VR-GUss to access the same video from the cloud [291]. Another interesting use case could be the deployment of UAVs in an ultra-dense area where satellites fail to provide the geographic locations or inside large mines, where UAVs enable localization and transmit live video simultaneously [292].

2) Laser Mapping and HD Patrol

The term laser means light amplification by stimulating the emission of radiation, which is proclaimed for the generation or amplification of light. This technology is used in various fields for plenty of applications, such as surgery in medicine, cutting, drilling, ranging, and many more. It is also used in 3D scanning and mapping based on the emission, detection, and ranging known as Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) technology. UAVs can be used with LiDAR technology for 3D mapping for different applications, such as land surveying, mine mapping, and agriculture purposes.

A low-cost 3D mapping system was tested in Dongtai forest in Jiangsu, China, for addressing the 3D mapping and tree characterization problems [293]. They used the DJI M600Pro Hexa-rotor UAV, equipped with a VLP-16 laser scanner and Flea3 Camera. The point clouds were reconstructed in a mapping frame using MATLAB, and the results with the proposed algorithm are better than the loosely coupled Kalman filter. Furthermore, they also characterized the trees individually. The same problem has been addressed with UAVs in amalgamation with a terrestrial of sensors for detailed characterization [294], and the model is tested in two different Australian tropical rainforests. Another model is presented for open-pit mine 3D mapping and monitoring in which UAVs are used for capturing photos, and a network of terrestrial laser sensors are used for ranging [295]. The proposed model is named Photogrammetry integrated with Terrestrial Laser sensing (TLS) and used for monitoring, mapping, and planning for mining locations.

In 6G, the NTN will be used with terrestrial networks and can also be used for localization of UAVs [296], localization and mapping via UAVs [297], [298], navigation in GPS-denied zones [299] and with integrated with GPS [300], [301]. The localization problem is taken into consideration in 6G, and researchers are trying to address it using mmwave [302], [303], and THz [304]. A summary of the open issue and future challenges in simultaneous localization and

mapping in future wireless networks has been provided in [305]. *Table 8 summarizes the applications of UAVs in 3D mapping and navigation, exploring their diverse roles in improving spatial awareness and positioning accuracy. The table categorizes the scope of these applications into key areas such as 3D mapping, localization, combined localization and mapping, and navigation. It also highlights UAV contributions to advanced navigation solutions, emphasizing their critical role in real-time and precise movement planning across complex terrains. This structured overview provides a clear understanding of the advancements and research trends in UAV-based mapping and navigation systems.*

TABLE 8. UAV application in 3D mapping and navigation

Scope	Papers
3D Mapping	[293], [294], [295]
Localization	[296],
Localization and Mapping	[297], [298], [302], [304]
Navigation	[299], [301]

3) Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Surveillance

UAVs and AI are important technologies and can be combined to generate an effective and efficient model for surveillance services in military and civil applications. In this model, UAVs are equipped with sensors and cameras for real-time imaging, processing and analysis, which allows an automated surveillance system and detects potential security threats against UAVs [306]. The sensor suite captures high-resolution images and videos and can transmit them in real time to permit automated surveillance. The design parameters, such as payload capacity, flight time, and stability of the UAV, should be considered when modeling the AI surveillance system.

The security aspects need to be considered while designing AI algorithms with the ability to identify potential security threats with reliability and high accuracy. The threats can also be classified into physical threats to the UAV platform and communications threats. The physical threats can be handled with the help of efficient and complex algorithms, but the communications threats are tricky to tackle. An AI-powered communication model for a UAV-enabled monitoring system is designed to secure the communication payloads from unauthorized users [307]. The security in UAV networks using 5G services can also be ensured through the blockchain concept in combination with AI, where a platform for data storage can be used and communicate with the security and privacy concerns [308]. Another model is proposed in [309] to ensure the physical security of the UAV, and laser technology is used for 3D mapping for surveillance in the forest regions. The optimal and efficient planning and implementation of AI-powered surveillance with UAVs can provide significant benefits and efficacy in security. However,

privacy concerns, potential risks and regulatory issues must be considered as a design paradigm with SWaP.

B. Command and Control

The Command and Control (C2) system of a UAV is responsible for the communication between the ground station and the UAV and permits it to be controlled by the operator remotely based on its performance. The communication link can be LOS or NLOS, depending on the range and requirements of the mission. This C2 link should be secure, reliable and with enough bandwidth to support real-time trajectory and other mission requirements. The UAV's program should be responsive and have the ability to be overridden with the C2 link for change in trajectory or according to mission needs. The C2 link can be challenging due to factors, such as limited range, cybersecurity risks, and potential interference from other communication devices. The interference problem can be tackled with the help of handover to Unmanned Aircraft System Traffic Management (UTM) from the C2 link usually authorized by aircraft system nodes and flight plans [310]. Nevertheless, authentication and encryption for C2 links with countermeasures for pathloss can be used to secure and enable predictive operations [311]. These encryption techniques should be strong enough to avoid all unauthenticated requests, especially in battles where variable devices along with combat vehicles, are interconnected. In such a scenario, semantic-oriented approaches, such as information-centric and delay-tolerant networks can outperform the existing security approaches used for C2 link [312].

1) Remote UAV Controller through HD Video

Remote UAV controllers through HD video is a useful and practical solution for controlling UAVs from a distance. By transmitting high-quality video in real-time, operators can remotely view the UAV's surroundings and control its movements accordingly. This is particularly useful for situations where the operator needs to navigate the UAV through complex environments or perform tasks requiring high situational awareness.

However, using HD video for remote UAV control also presents challenges, particularly concerning data transmission and bandwidth requirements. HD video requires significant bandwidth, making it difficult to maintain a reliable data link over long distances or in areas with poor connectivity. Additionally, video transmission can be affected by interference, latency, and other factors that can impact the quality of the video and, consequently, the operator's ability to control the UAV effectively. To address these challenges, ensuring that the data link is reliable and secure, with sufficient bandwidth to support HD video transmission, is important. This can involve encryption, frequency hopping, authentication, firewalls, and physical security measures to protect the data link from unauthorized access and interference. Additionally, using advanced video compression techniques

and other optimization methods can help reduce bandwidth requirements and improve video transmission quality.

Overall, remote UAV control through HD video has the potential to be a highly effective and efficient way to control UAVs from a distance. However, ensuring that the data link is secure and reliable and that appropriate measures are taken to address any challenges associated with HD video transmission is important.

2) Automatic Flight on UTM

UTM for automatic flight UAVs is increasingly important for safe and efficient operations. UTM is a system that manages the airspace for UAVs and ensures that they can operate safely and effectively alongside manned aircraft. UTM can support automatic flight by providing real-time airspace information to the UAV, including weather conditions, airspace restrictions, and other relevant data [313]. This enables the UAV to adjust its flight path automatically and avoid potential hazards or conflicts with other aircraft. Additionally, UTM can facilitate automatic flight by providing communication links between the UAV and Ground Control Stations (GCS), enabling operators to control the UAV's movements and monitor its performance remotely. This can involve using advanced technologies such as ML, AI, and data analytics to optimize UAV flight paths, improve safety, and enhance operational efficiency.

However, using automatic flight in UTM also presents some challenges concerning safety and security. It is important to ensure the UAV is equipped with reliable sensors, communication links, and other systems to enable safe and efficient autonomous flight. Encryption, authentication, and other security measures can help protect the UAV and its data from unauthorized access or interference. Overall, using UTM for the automatic flight of UAVs has the potential to revolutionize how UAVs are operated and managed. However, it is important to ensure that appropriate safety and security measures are in place to support reliable and effective UAV operations.

VI. Challenges in UAV-wireless communications

Despite numerous advantages, UAV-based communication systems face challenges that must be addressed to fully realize their potential. These challenges span multiple dimensions, including transmission distortion, interference, and multiple antenna systems. Ensuring secure communication, particularly in dynamic environments, remains a concern, as UAVs are vulnerable to various security threats, including eavesdropping and jamming, which highlights the need for robust PLS mechanisms. Additionally, interference management becomes complex when UAVs operate in crowded or dense networks, where their mobility introduces rapid fluctuations in signal quality and link stability. Addressing these issues is crucial for enabling the seamless integration of UAVs in future communication networks.

A. Impact of Transmission Distortion

The impact of transmission distortion on UAV communications differs from terrestrial networks in several ways. Primarily, UAV communications typically involve a much smaller coverage area than terrestrial networks, as UAVs typically operate within a limited range of the GCS. This can result in higher signal attenuation and interference, particularly in urban or densely populated environments with many obstacles and wireless devices competing for bandwidth. Secondly, UAV communications is often subject to higher mobility than terrestrial networks, as UAVs are designed to move through the air at varying altitudes and speeds. This can result in rapid signal strength and multipath propagation changes, leading to increased signal distortion and lower data rates. Furthermore, UAV communications often operate on different frequency bands than terrestrial networks, which can have different propagation characteristics and susceptibility to interference. For example, UAVs may operate on frequencies in the unlicensed spectrum, which can be subject to interference from other wireless devices.

Overall, the impact of transmission distortion on UAV communications differs from terrestrial networks due to the unique characteristics of the UAV communications environment, including limited coverage area, high mobility, different frequency bands, and different modulation and coding requirements. To ensure reliable and high-quality communications in UAVs, it is important to use appropriate mitigation techniques tailored to the UAV communications environment.

B. Impact of Interference

The mitigation of interference in UAV-enabled wireless communications requires a combination of different techniques tailored to the specific application and operating environment. By carefully selecting the appropriate frequency band, antenna design, power control, coding and modulation techniques, and channel allocation, the impact of interference can be minimized, improving the reliability and quality of the data link between the UAV and the GCS.

C. Multiple Antennas on UAV

[314] Due to the SWaP constraints over UAVs, the challenges in the installation of multiple antennas over UAVs can be analyzed in two different cases. Multiple antennas are required on UAVs for different purposes, such as GPS triangulation, C2 link, and other communication purposes, which can affect each other's performance. The solution to this problem is to install antennas in optimal positions and significantly distance apart, as well as use different communication bands to reduce the interference. In the second case, multiple antennas can be installed on UAVs for spatial diversity to increase the communication's coverage area, and improve the signal strength and spectral efficiency. Hence, enhanced communication capabilities enable one to operate in more challenging environments with trade-offs on

power consumption, complexity, and cost. Furthermore, to manage interference, several challenges, such as the position of antennas and mechanical and electrical tilts, need to be carefully considered and addressed to ensure optimal performance.

VII. Implementation Issues

The NTN supports terrestrial networks to enable wireless communications and provide reliable connectivity, fulfilling 6G requirements. However, due to the different nature of the environment on each layer in NTN networks, the channel models and propagation environment are challenging. For example, the communication link from the satellite to HAP differs from the link to LAP, and similarly, the link towards ground/ ocean users is different. Keeping different path-loss models in consideration with different distances among NTN layers, different frequency bands, multiple access techniques, and different power allocation strategies are used. Furthermore, the concept of Open-Radio Access Network (ORAN) proposed for 5G, has introduced more complexity of interoperability to NTN communications. A few of the challenges and issues faced in implementation and testing are identified in the following subsections.

A. Error Propagation

One of the most critical implementation issues in NTN is the heightened susceptibility to error propagation due to factors, such as long signal travel distances and challenging environmental conditions. The latency inherent in these networks often leads to significant delays in error detection and recovery, thereby exacerbating the propagation of errors across the system. This problem is further intensified by the lack of reliable, real-time feedback mechanisms and the limitations of traditional error-correcting codes, necessitating specialized algorithms for extreme conditions such as cosmic radiation. Bandwidth limitations and the cost of implementing robust error-correction techniques—especially given the power and computational constraints of NTN nodes, such as satellites—further complicate the issue. Despite these challenges, addressing error propagation is vital for the success of next-generation communication systems, especially as reliance on space-based infrastructure for global connectivity grows.

B. Power Allocation Complexity

NTN operates in dynamic and heterogeneous environments with variable link conditions, including satellite-to-satellite, satellite-to-ground, satellite-to-UAV, and UAV-to-ground. Keeping different scenarios in consideration for different applications, it is quite clear that the energy utilization would be different for effective communication, impacting EE. This problem can be solved with the help of mixed integer non-linear programming followed by algorithms for decomposition and solution [315]. Some NTN platforms, like LAPs and HAPs, have limited power budgets on board,

which can be resolved through dynamic power allocation schemes that allocate energy resources based on the channel condition and QoS requirements with constraints on the available energy source, helping in maximum platform longevity. Saafi and co-authors presented the same concept based on ML to deal with the dynamic resource allocation for sustainable maritime networking [316]. Another resource allocation and user association model based on deep RL in NTN and TN is used by exploiting the different channel models, mobility scenarios, and delay QoS models [317]. The power allocation becomes more complex when it comes to ensuring security and maximizing the secrecy rate of legitimate users.

C. Residual Timing Offsets

The received signal in the Single-Input-Single-Output (SISO) system is affected by one timing offset, while in the MIMO system, multiple timing offsets affect the received signal. The receiver must estimate and compensate for these parameters to decode the received signal successfully. One of the key constraints for residual timing offset or carrier synchronization is the frequency/ timing error. According to release 17 of 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP), the frequency error is observed to be ± 0.1 Pulse Position Modulation (PPM) over a period of 1 millisecond and over a period of 0.5 milliseconds in the case of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) synchronization source [318]. Due to high mobility in NTN systems, $\sim 20\%$ of PPM budget is allocated for the compensation of error due to Doppler in order to satisfy the standards [319].

D. Signaling and Processing Overhead

Signaling and processing overheads in NTN wireless communications can have various significant effects on the overall link performance, resulting in reduced spectral efficiency, resource contentions and increased latency. Signaling overhead is particularly pronounced in scenarios involving handover between different NTN nodes and terrestrial nodes. Nevertheless, the excessive signaling affects and could introduce delays to handover procedures, impacting the QoS for mobile users and causing potential service disruptions. To address the signaling overhead, an automatic repeat request scheduling for NTN is proposed in [320], while the processing overhead can be dealt with the estimation and demodulation techniques to support high mobility in NTN communications [321]. Signaling overhead can improve the secrecy with the trade-off on capacity.

E. UAVs deploying Environment

The maneuverability is the advantage of NTN wireless communications over terrestrial networks. Nevertheless, this can also introduce some limitations, such as the limited power on board, and the dynamic flights can lead the user to the communication link being affected, resulting in a loss of reliability. Furthermore, the dynamics in the environment and

maneuverability of drones could affect the smooth handover and the susceptance to interference. These issues can be resolved by channel modeling with directional antenna modeling, which is not sensitive to LOS blockage [322]. Another approach to resolve these issues could be 3D placement modeling, as [323] proposed efficient 3D placement with the help of a genetic algorithm. Recently, the environmental effects on PLS have been studied in [324].

Apart from the communication challenges, the harsh environmental condition is also a challenge in UAV deployment. UAV operations in high altitudes, extreme temperatures, and adverse weather must be robust enough to withstand these conditions. Recently published research reported the testing of UAV operations in the harsh conditions of the Livingston Island Glaciers, Antarctica [325]. They analyze the stability and jittering under gusty winds, the battery life, and the flight for very long distances, i.e., 60 Km in 50 minutes. This research shows the potential of UAVs to be deployed in remote areas with harsh conditions, which opens the door for new usage scenarios, despite the need for further research.

F. Standardization Landscape

Integrating UAVs and NTN into the 3GPP standardization process heralded a pivotal evolution from traditional terrestrial-centric cellular frameworks to a more encompassing paradigm that includes airborne and non-terrestrial environments. Presently, the majority of satellite communications rely on specialized, custom-made systems. However, this trend might be on the verge of transformation and put focus on the need to address various aspects of UAV communications, considering the unique requirements and challenges associated with UAV deployments. NTN is first considered in 3GPP Release 17, setting a robust groundwork for direct interaction among satellites, smartphones, and various widely accessible user devices. However, the study on NTN integration and support in New Radio (NR) was initiated in Release 15, based on which solutions were proposed later in Release 16. In Release 17, the coexistence aspects are investigated for a case where satellites operate complementary to NTN and in remote locations where satellites and NTN operate in adjacent bands. A challenging scenario could be when a GU communicates with a satellite while not being a part of NTN and using an adjacent band of NTN, and still, the beams overlap in the downlink (reference: TR 38.821 and TR 38.811).

The regulatory requirements in wireless communications in terms of latency, reliability, accuracy, and, most importantly, privacy regarding customers' localization services for various use cases are addressed in Release 18 (reference: TS 22.261, TR 23.737, and TR 22.926), sketched in Table 9. *According to the technical report of the fourth quarter of 2023, the objective was to define the bands into 3GPP specifications. These discussions resulted in the addition of two NTN bands, the L-band and S-band, designated as bands n255 and n256, respectively. Simultaneously, there are other*

satellite deployments, some of which utilize a mixed L-/S-band pairing, with the UL on the L-band and the DL on the S-band.

TABLE 9. Standardization: use cases and requirements set in Release 18

Service	Accuracy	Reliability	Latency
Emergency Call	According to EC [326], 3m vertical and 50m horizontal with 5m and 25m error in open sky and urban canyon, respectively. Additionally, $\pm 3\%$ applies in FCC [327].	Mobile Network Operator (MNO) may be liable to provision	\leq second.
Lawful Intercept (TS 33.126)	Comparable with TN	MNO shall be able to provision	No requirement but comparable to TN
Public Warning Service (TS 22.268)	Targeted area with macro cell size granularity	No requirement but comparable to TN	No requirement but comparable to TN
Charging and Tariff notification	Similar to TN, so Macro cell size granularity	MNO to ensure	Should be equivalent to TN

According to the privacy law given in [328], the location of the UE, i.e., GU and AUE, should be protected in the provision of the users’ privacy. The 3GPP releases on NTN standardization are summarized in Table. 10.

VIII. Lessons Learned

The survey highlights the potential of UAVs to enhance NTN communication through flexibility, adaptability, and integration with emerging technologies such as RIS and ML. However, it also underscores the importance of addressing challenges related to energy management, security, privacy, computational constraints, and regulatory compliance. In this section, we summarize the lessons learned while conducting this survey, which are given below.

- **Flexibility and adaptability** are the more important aspects of using UAVs in NTN wireless communications because of the quick and flexible deployment infrastructure, especially in emergency situations and remote areas. This dynamic property enables the UAV to adjust its position according to the demands, significantly improving the network performance. However, ML can be used to detect spoofing attacks and counteract them with resilient positioning capabilities.
- **Security at the physical layer** is inevitable and crucial in NTN wireless communications as it provides seamless and infrastructure-less security. The 6G wireless networks aim to provide simultaneous ultra-high speed

TABLE 10. 3GPP timeline on NTN standardization

Year	Report	Release	Description
2017 - 2018	TR 38.811	Rel-15	Study on NR to support NTN including, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background overview • Deployment scenarios • Channel models • Key impacts on NR to support NTN • Directions for advancement
2018 - 2019	TR 38.821	Rel-16	Solutions for NR to support NTN
2020 - 2021	TR 38.863	Rel-17	NTN related RF and co-existence aspect
2021 - 2022	TR 38.882	Rel-18	Study of use cases or network verified UT
2023 - 2024	- TR 38.741 - SA1 Study (Rel-20)	Rel-19 & Rel-20	- L- and S-bands were discussed, L-band for UL while S-band for DL. - 6G Architecture Opt. Decision?
2025	SA1 Requirement WI (Rel-21)		
2026	SA2 Tech. S1		

and reliable connectivity supporting integrated NTN and terrestrial networks. However, an extensively connected decentralized 3D network requires a decentralized security solution due to SWaP constraints, which can only be possible with seamless and infrastructure-less PLS. The PLS is further categorized into key-based and keyless approaches, and the comparison is given in Table 5.

- **Robust authentication** is essential for ensuring the security of the communication link and verifying the identities of communicating parties. The random channel samples can be exploited to generate the secret keys, and the randomness can be validated through the NIST test suite. However, ML algorithms can ensure the highest level of accuracy and enhanced security with the help of dynamic adaptation. The challenges of using ML in SKG are computational overhead, complexity, and privacy of the data collected and processed for training.
- **Privacy and data security** is another critical concern as UAVs collect, process, and transmit vast amounts of data, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of this data is paramount. Addressing these concerns involves implementing robust security protocols, encryption techniques, and privacy-preserving measures to protect against potential threats and vulnerabilities. Ultimately, prioritizing privacy and data security is

essential for the successful and sustainable deployment of UAV-enabled NTN, enabling the realization of its full potential in a secure and trustworthy manner.

- **Integration with existing and emerging technologies** plays a pivotal role in the deployment and expansion of beyond 5G networks, providing enhanced coverage, high data rate, and reliable connectivity. Integrating UAV-enabled NTN communications with existing and emerging technologies can provide numerous benefits, including enhanced connectivity, improved data processing capabilities, greater security, and increased operational efficiency. By leveraging these technologies, UAVs can play a more significant role in expanding the reach and capabilities of NTN communications, supporting a wide range of applications and services in both urban and remote environments, as discussed in detail in Section IV.
- **Collaborative approach** can significantly enhance NTN wireless communication by exploring shared resources, optimizing network performance, and improving reliability. Collaborative approaches such as resource sharing, traffic management, interference management, scalability, flexibility, and seamless handover strategies enhance network efficiency, reliability, and scalability, ensuring robust and high-quality communication services across various scenarios and environments.
- **Practical deployment considerations** encompass a wide range of factors, including regulatory compliance, integration with existing infrastructure, security, and operational efficiency. These considerations are crucial for maximizing the benefits of UAVs in NTN while minimizing potential risks and obstacles. Effective deployment of UAVs necessitates a holistic approach addressing technical and non-technical factors. By carefully planning and executing deployment strategies, stakeholders can harness the full potential of UAVs to extend connectivity, enhance network resilience, and support a diverse array of applications. Emphasizing regulatory compliance, robust security measures, seamless integration with existing technologies, and efficient operational practices will ensure the sustainable and scalable implementation of UAVs, ultimately driving innovation and connectivity in urban and remote regions.

These lessons provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state, challenges, and future directions in the field, guiding researchers and practitioners in developing more effective UAV-based NTN communication systems.

IX. Conclusion

In the ongoing technological renaissance, we are witnessing the profound emergence of the IoTs alongside the advent of Industry 5.0. Projections indicate that interconnected devices will exceed 30 billion by 2030, marking a paradigm shift in our digital era. Despite the transformative potentials

of 5G networks, reliability in terms of connectivity and capacity to accommodate a number of billion more devices remains a challenge, especially in remote and disaster areas. Addressing these shortcomings, the technological frontier appears ready to embrace 6G, which aspires for impeccable AI convergence, enhanced security, and expansive global reach. NTN integration into 5G and Beyond wireless systems has been considered by standardization bodies, such as 3GPP, since Release 17 that UAVs lauded for their adaptability and multifaceted utility, yet open to security dreads as infrastructure-based security is not an appropriate solution due to SWaP limitations. UAVs have been a focus of prominent research interest as NTNs of great potential to be integrated for a variety of usage scenarios with terrestrial networks. This paper explored their capabilities and focused on open challenges related to UAV security as a key requirement for unleashing the full potential of UAVs. Furthermore, a comprehensive literature review is carried out, focused on PLS. Beginning with the 3D channel modeling and tutorial of PLS to state-of-the-art 6G technologies in NTN, PLS perspectives have been emphasized. Furthermore, different use case scenarios and performance evaluations of UAVs are discussed. The open issues and challenges in NTN communications and UAV deployments in NTN are also discussed. In conclusion, we methodically scrutinized the ascent and prospective trajectories of a number of connected devices alongside advancements in communication networks, highlighting the constraints of 5G and the potential capabilities of 6G. Furthermore, we explored the instrumental role of UAVs within NTN, accentuating the imperatives and prospects tied to fortified security measures.

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